

COMPASS

Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Deliverable 2.2

31st August 2025

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Title	Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers
Lead Beneficiary	Met Office
Lead Author(s)	Isabel Rushby, Daniel Etheridge (Met Office)
Contributors	Rachel Perks, Dan Bernie, Gregory Munday, Daniel Cotterill (Met Office)
Deliverable number	2.2
Work Package	WP2: Attribution frameworks in a physical context
Submission date	31/08/2025

Dissemination Level

PU	Public — fully open (automatically posted online)	X
SEN	Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
CI	EU classified — Restreint-UE/EU-Restricted, Confidentiel-UE/EU-Confidential, Secret-UE/EU-Secret under Decision 2015/444	

Version History

Date	Version	Contributors	Comments
31/07/2025	0.1	Isabel Rushby, Daniel Etheridge, Rachel Perks, Dan Bernie, Gregory Munday, Daniel Cotterill (Met Office)	First version for internal review
20/08/2025	0.2	Maggie Kossida (SEVEN), Edward Pope (Met Office)	Internal review
28/08/2025	1.0	Isabel Rushby, Daniel Etheridge (Met Office)	Final review and first finished version

Citation

Rushby, I., Etheridge, D., Perks, R., Bernie, D., Munday, G., Cotterill, D. (2025): Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers. Horizon Europe project COMPASS. Deliverable D2.2.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Funded by the
European Union

The COMPASS project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101135481

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority HADEA can be held responsible for them

Executive summary

The COMPASS project aims to develop a harmonized but flexible methodological framework for climate and impact attribution of various hazard types, going beyond existing frameworks by moving from attribution of single-driver extremes to the attribution of more complex extremes (i.e. compound, sequences and cascading hazard events). The project also aims to enable a shift from hazard centered analysis to an impact-centered perspective. The goal of Work Package 2 of the COMPASS project is to develop a physical understanding of the drivers of compound extremes using weather type analysis and subsequently apply a variety of event attribution methods to consider relevant impacts of compound events.

This report, deliverable D2.2, presents a novel framework (outlined in Figure 1) to identify, assess and understand large-scale drivers which give rise to compound extremes, utilising weather patterns to bridge the gap. Improving understanding of the large-scale drivers of compound events is crucial to operationalising the climate and impact attribution of these events. However, it is challenging to directly link large-scale drivers of climate variability to compound events. Weather patterns, a set of atmospheric circulation types over a defined geographical region on a given day, are an established method used to assess the conditions that give rise to weather extremes. A significant amount research on weather patterns exists that links meteorological hazard to their associated impacts. Here, we propose a framework to extend this research to understand the large-scale drivers of compound events and pave the way for future climate and impact attribution studies.

Figure 1: Schematic of the COMPASS framework, showing the steps required to understand and quantify the influence of large-scale drivers of a compound event.

This report presents a demonstration of the COMPASS framework for a case study of the 2013/2014 UK winter storms, a discussion of the findings and recommendations for future work. In addition, we have conducted research which begins to explore whether weather patterns remain consistent over long time periods to be reliably used in climate attribution studies. It aims to clarify what is meant by non-stationarity and identify the main challenges and uncertainties in assessing it.

Key findings – case study demonstration:

- There are statistically significant associations between a set of large-scale drivers of winter North Atlantic atmospheric circulation and a previously defined, well-used set of daily weather patterns for circulation over the UK (Neal et al., 2016).

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

- A review of the literature shows that weather patterns 29 (cyclonic south–south-westerly with a deep low centre of pressure west of Ireland) and 30 (cyclonic west-north-westerly with deep low pressure southeast of Iceland) from Neal et al. (2016) are linked to the 2013/2014 winter storms in the UK.
- Whilst the performance of the large-scale drivers in predicting the frequency of weather patterns 29 and 30 in January and February through an initial causal network is poor, a number of areas for further research and improvements have been identified.

Key findings – assessing the stationarity of weather patterns:

- We use a machine learning clustering algorithm to create historical weather patterns for the UK based on mean sea level pressure data. These patterns are compared across different time windows to a set of reference patterns to assess how they differ. Our findings suggest that some of the spatial patterns of generated clusters show changes across time windows over the last 40 years. However, it is currently not possible to determine whether these changes reflect real shifts, natural variability, or limitations of the method itself.
- This research highlights the complexity and uncertainty involved in assessing weather pattern stationarity and suggests that using weather patterns as constraints – and the assumption of stationarity – in climate attribution should be done with caution and warrants further research.

This report is closely linked to deliverable D2.3 *“Dataset on weather types and largescale climate drivers”*, which facilitates the analysis of relationships between UK weather types and large-scale drivers relevant to winter North Atlantic circulation. Both D2.2 and D2.3 contribute to one of COMPASS’s specific objective SO2.2 *“Work towards development of a framework to identify, assess and understand large scale drivers and mechanisms which give rise to compound extremes”*.

Table of Contents

Executive summary	4
Glossary	8
1. Introduction.....	10
2. The COMPASS framework for linking large-scale drivers to compound events	13
2.2 Exploration of relationships between large-scale drivers and weather patterns	15
2.3 Assessment of stationarity of weather patterns.....	15
2.4 Exploration of relationships between weather patterns and compound events	16
2.5 Identification of focus weather patterns.....	17
2.65 Estimating causal effects of large-scale drivers on focus WPs	17
2.76 Quantifying the impact of large-scale drivers on compound events	17
3. Applying the COMPASS Framework: Dataset for linking large-scale drivers and weather patterns in the UK 19	
3.1. Data	19
3.1.1. Large scale drivers	19
3.1.2. Weather Patterns	21
3.2. Method	24
4. Large-scale drivers and weather patterns.....	26
5. Stationarity of weather patterns.....	36
5.1. Stationarity	36
5.2. Methodology	36
5.3. Configuration.....	38
5.4. Sources of uncertainty.....	39
5.5. Results	40
5.6. Discussion	54
6. Weather patterns to hazards	57
7. Case study.....	64
7.1. Methods	64
7.2. Results	65
7.2.1. Correlation.....	65
7.2.2. Casual inference	71
8. Discussion	79
Key findings	79
Challenges.....	79

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Next steps.....80

9. Conclusion83

10. References.....85

11. Annex A: Relationships between large-scale drivers and WPs89

12. Annex B: Diagnostics of multiple linear regression models for Case Study106

Glossary

AleutLow	Aleutian Low, a large-scale driver
ASO	August-September-October
Association	A statistical relationship between two variables, which can either be positive or negative
AtlDip	Atlantic Dipole, a large-scale driver
AtlJet	Atlantic Jet, a large-scale driver
BKSIC	Barents-Kara Sea Ice Concentration, a large-scale driver
Causal inference	An area of statistics which develops methods to determine whether changes in one variable directly result in changes to another
Causal network	A description of the causal links between a set of variables using one-way arrows
Climate change	A large-scale, long-term shift in the planet's weather patterns and average temperatures
Climate variability	Periodic variations in climate on annual to multi-decadal timescales, but shorter-term than climate change timescales. This could be due to natural variations, or other factors such as volcanic eruptions.
Correlation	A statistical measure of the relationship multiple variables, which can either be positive or negative and linear or non-linear. For example, Pearson's correlation coefficient or Spearman's rank correlation coefficient.
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph, a way of graphically representing a causal network
Decider	A medium-to long-range ensemble forecasting tool in use at the Met Office, based on the MO30 (Neal et al., 2016)
Distance	A metric for comparing weather patterns, the area weighted grid-point average sum-of-squares difference (Neal et al., 2016)
DJF	December-January-February
EMSLP	European and North Atlantic Daily to Multi-decadal Climate Variability (EMULATE) MSLP (EMSLP) dataset (Ansell et al., 2006)
ENSO	El Niño Southern Oscillation, a large-scale driver
ERA5	The European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) Reanalysis v5 (Hersbach et al., 2020)
IOD	Indian Ocean Dipole, a large-scale driver
JF	January-February
Large-scale driver	Aspects of the global weather and climate system than are predictable, with different influences on the UK and global weather.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

LSAP	Linear Sum Assignment Problem
MO8	The set of 8 canonical weather patterns in use at the Met Office, for evaluating long-range and seasonal forecasts
MO30	The set of 30 canonical weather patterns in use at the Met Office, primarily for evaluating medium-range forecasts
MSLP	Mean Sea Level Pressure
NAO	North Atlantic Oscillation, a large-scale driver or mode of variability
OND	October-November-December
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
QBO	Quasi-biennial Oscillation, a large-scale driver
SCM	Structured Causal Model, a set of equations used to specify a causal network
SON	September-October-November
SPV	Stratospheric Polar Vortex, a large-scale driver
Stationarity	Where the characteristics of a phenomenon are constant in time.
Statistical significance	Results are referred to as statistically significant if hypothesis testing has showed that findings are sufficiently unlikely to have been found without true differences or relationships existing.
UralsMSLP	Urals Mean Sea Level Pressure, a large-scale driver
WP	Weather Pattern

1. Introduction

Extreme weather events are often linked to large-scale atmospheric flow or a specific "weather type". A weather pattern (referred to as WP throughout this report) is one of many synoptic-scale atmospheric circulation types over a defined geographical region on a given day (Neal et al., 2016). Because each daily WP has its own associated climatological characteristics (e.g. temperature and precipitation), a given pattern can be translated into expected weather impacts for a particular region (Pope et al., 2022). More generally, each weather pattern will be associated with a distribution of meteorological characteristics. Neal et al. (2016) used an objective approach to create a set of 30 frequently occurring WPs covering the UK and surrounding European area; the patterns have been used by the Met Office for several years as part of the Decider forecasting tool¹ and are referred to as the MO30².

There is a significant amount of research assessing the conditions that give rise to weather extremes, and their relationships with WPs (in particular the MO30). These are used in operational forecasts, and research applications for various hazards (e.g. storm surges, landslides, offshore waves and heat related mortality; Huang et al., 2020; Neal et al., 2018; Steele et al., 2018). WPs are also used to understand atmospheric variability on climate change time scales, including frequency and seasonality of periods of elevated flood risk, as a result of changing atmospheric circulation patterns and changing frequency of specific circulation patterns (Cotterill et al., 2023; Perks et al., 2023). To a lesser extent, WPs have also been used internationally, for example WPs have been created to research heat-related impacts in South Africa (Ireland et al., 2024) and precipitation in India (Neal et al., 2020).

One of the goals of the COMPASS project is to develop a physical understanding of the drivers of compound extremes using weather type analysis and subsequently apply a variety of event attribution methods to consider relevant impacts of compound events. There are several ways in which climate attribution studies of compound events could benefit from a greater understanding of large-scale drivers. These include selecting

1 Decider is a probabilistic weather pattern forecasting tool that can be used for applications where a relationship can be established between weather conditions or impacts, and historical weather pattern data. It helps to predict future weather conditions or impacts by assisting with the interpretation of the large amounts of probabilistic data provided by ensemble forecasting systems.

2 MO30 or the Met Office 30 Weather Patterns, is a set of 30 patterns derived through k-means clustering of daily mean sea level pressure (MSLP) data (1850–2003) and ordered by frequency—WP1 being most frequent and WP30 least. These patterns have been designed for the purpose of post-processing forecast output from ensemble prediction systems and understanding how forecast models perform under different circulation types. The MO30 can also be categorised into eight sub-patterns, referred to as the MO8. The 30 weather patterns are designed for use in the medium-range and the eight weather patterns are designed for use in the monthly and seasonal timescales, or when there is low forecast confidence in the medium-range (Neal et al., 2016).

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

analogues for conditional attribution studies, supporting the validation of an attribution study by building confidence in the mechanisms behind observational events and the fidelity of their modelled counterparts, and understanding the relative contribution of thermodynamic and large-scale dynamic changes to overall changes in the probability of an event. However, it is challenging to directly link large-scale drivers to compound events. Meanwhile, the wealth of research into hazards and impacts associated with regional WPs provides an opportunity to better understand the drivers of compound events – if a link can be established between large-scale drivers and regional WPs. This report, “D2.2 – Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers”, presents the novel COMPASS framework to identify, assess and understand large-scale drivers which give rise to compound extremes, utilising WPs to bridge the gap. Additionally, it aims to extend the weather type approach to consider compound events for specific geographies and to understand associated drivers – such as meridional temperature gradients, patterns of heat and moisture storage, and polar vortex strength – with potential to develop a conditional approach to the attribution of compound events. To our knowledge, this is the first research to link large-scale drivers to compound events in this way.

Stationarity of WPs – i.e. consistency in their spatial structure and frequency over time - is a key assumption behind their use in many studies, including the potential use in conditional attribution studies, where they could serve as reliable constraints in likelihood calculations. This report begins to explore the assumption of WP stationarity for the past four decades. These insights aim to help clarify the suitability of WPs as a tool for connecting large-scale drivers and compound events.

Box 1. Why do we want to link large-scale drivers, weather patterns and compound events?
1. Large-scale drivers set the stage

- a. Modes of variability like the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), the El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO), or the Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) influence the overall atmospheric circulation across regions and seasons.
- b. These drivers do not cause a flood or heatwave directly, but they tilt the odds towards stormier, wetter, hotter, or drier conditions.

2. Weather patterns translate drivers into local impacts

- a. Weather patterns (like the MO30 set for the UK) describe the synoptic-scale configurations of pressure systems (e.g. a deep low west of Ireland, a blocking high over Scandinavia).
- b. These patterns are the “bridge”: they capture how large-scale drivers manifest in the atmosphere above a specific region.
- c. Because each pattern is associated with typical weather outcomes (wet, dry, stormy, calm), they provide a practical link between global-scale variability and regional hazards.

3. Compound events are the end result

- a. Many damaging events (e.g. coastal flooding, heatwave + drought, snow + cold extremes) arise from the co-occurrence of multiple hazards.
- b. By linking drivers → weather patterns → hazards, we could better quantify how likely these compound events are under certain climate states.

Why does this matter for attribution and risk management?

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Without the “bridge” of weather patterns, it is difficult to directly connect large-scale climate variability to local compound impacts. Weather patterns could allow us to:

- Condition attribution studies on the circulation states most relevant to an event.
- Improve early warnings, because if a large-scale driver is known to favour certain patterns, forecasters can anticipate clusters of hazardous days.
- Assess climate change impacts, by testing whether the frequency or structure of patterns themselves are shifting, and what that implies for risks.

The COMPASS framework could be applied to any region where a set of WPs have been or could be produced; however, in this work we demonstrate its application to the UK using the MO30. In particular, we focus on winter compound flooding due to rainfall and storm surges, with the Somerset Levels flooding of 2013/2014 given as an example of how large-scale drivers can be used to estimate the probability of impactful WPs occurring (aligning with *D4.1 Hazard and Impact Synthesis and Attribution for Phase I - Use Case 2a*).

The structure of the report is as follows: Section 2 introduces the framework for identifying, assessing and understanding large-scale drivers and mechanisms which give rise to spatially or temporally compounding or multivariate compound extremes. Here we demonstrate the method for each step of the process, drawing insights from causal inference, a rapidly growing area of statistics. Section 3 describes the dataset for deliverable D3.3, including the data it is constructed from and the methods used. The dataset links large-scale drivers of winter North Atlantic atmospheric circulation with WPs relevant for weather conditions in the UK. Section 4 presents an analysis of the relationships between the large-scale drivers and the WPs included in the dataset. Section 5 presents an initial exploration of the assessment of the stationarity of the WPs included in the dataset. Section 6 reviews existing studies on the links between WPs in the UK and winter hazards, including compound events. Section 7 demonstrates the penultimate stage of the proposed framework, developing a causal network which links the large-scale drivers to WPs which are identified as related to the UK winter storms of 2013/2014 (refer to the case study 2a of the COMPASS report D4.1). Section 8 discusses the results of this report, the limitations of the work, and provides recommendations for future research. Finally, Section 9 provides concluding remarks.

This report is closely linked to the COMPASS dataset “*D2.3 - Dataset on weather types and largescale climate drivers*”, which combines existing UK-relevant WPs with large-scale drivers for North Atlantic circulation. The current report and datasets both contribute to one of COMPASS specific objective SO2.2 ‘*Work towards development of a framework to identify, assess and understand large scale drivers and mechanisms which give rise to compound extremes*’.

2. The COMPASS framework for linking large-scale drivers to compound events

Linking large-scale drivers, weather patterns and compound events has the potential to provide a more robust chain of understanding from global climate variability to local hazard risk: large-scale drivers represent year-to-year variability which affect regional circulation through teleconnections, weather patterns represent different types of regional circulation associated with distinct hazards, and compound events are the realised impacts of these hazards. Zscheischler et al. (2020) define four main types of compound events (preconditioned, multivariate, spatially compounding and temporally compounding) based on spatial and temporal characteristics. However, some compound events (such as tropical and extratropical cyclones) can fall under multiple types (Aleksandrova et al., 2024). The suggested COMPASS framework can be used to explore the conditional dependence of selected types of compound events on large-scale drivers. This is restricted to compound events where each of the contributing hazards, following the terminology of Zscheischler et al. (2020), have a common large-scale driver, or modulator. These compound events could fall under the multivariate, spatially compounding or temporally compounding types. The suggested framework could be used to identify large-scale drivers to be incorporated into conditional attribution studies for a certain type of compound event, or to provide standalone statements about the changing likelihood of an observed compound event due to the state of large-scale drivers in the preceding months. The steps of the COMPASS framework are outlined in Figure 2 and demonstrated in Sections 4 to 7.

Figure 2: Schematic of the COMPASS framework steps to understand and quantify the influence of large-scale drivers on a compound event.

The following sub-sections describe what is meant by each step of the framework and why they are required. They also provide a summary of possible approaches which could be applied to address each stage of the framework.

2.1 Selection of large-scale drivers

The first step, when applying the COMPASS framework to a chosen compound event of interest, is to select the relevant large-scale drivers³ (e.g. the El Niño Southern Oscillation, Indian Ocean Dipole, Madden-Julian

³ For a description of climate drivers and their influence on UK and global weather, see this Met Office explainer <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/services/government/contingency-planners/seasonal-forecasts-and-climate-drivers-resources>. Last accessed: 26/08/2025.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Oscillation, Quasi-Biennial Oscillation, Stratospheric Polar Vortex, etc.), including the months of the year over which the drivers are expected to have the largest effect. Winter coastal flooding in the UK is driven by heavy rainfall and storm surges, using this example one would need to select the large-scale drivers which are thought to lead to these conditions. As there can be a lag between a large-scale driver and its impact on UK atmospheric circulation, the relevant “predictor” months of the year would also need to be chosen, for example August-September-October could be the months that the teleconnection from ENSO has the most influence on winter North Atlantic circulation.

Many studies assess the relationships between different pairs of variables in the climate system, but it can be challenging to distil the key drivers from the research. In fact, teleconnections are often discovered by assessing the correlation between two variables, not accounting for other variables or providing a causal mechanism. This means that confounder bias may be creating spurious correlations between variables. According to causal inference, the process of determining the independent, actual effect of a particular phenomenon that is a component of a larger system, a causal hypothesis should be represented by a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) in order to define appropriate regression models which ensure that estimates of the causal effect of one variable upon another are unbiased. An introduction to causal inference is provided by Pearl et al. (2016).

Recent research has used causal networks (graphs which describe the causal links between variables) to combine information about multiple relevant drivers of variability (Kretschmer et al., 2016; Maher & Sherwood, 2014) or estimate teleconnections (Kretschmer et al., 2021). Most relevant for the example given above, Sexton et al. (2025) have constructed a causal network which represents the relationships between large-scale drivers which are related to winter North Atlantic circulation, including the size of the causal effects. However, this network does not extend beyond large-scale variability to specific weather types or compound events.

Developing a causal network is an iterative process, where implied conditional independencies between variables are tested and if necessary additional causal links are added. Causal independence means that two variables are independent, given that the value of a third variable is fixed. If X , Y , and Z are random variables with joint probability density function $p(x, y, z)$, then X and Y are conditionally independent given Z if the following equation holds:

$$p(x | y, z) = p(x | z)$$

Methods which can be used to test for conditional independence include linear conditional independence, conditional independence using loess regression, or chi-squared conditional independence in the case of categorical data (Textor et al., 2017).

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Once potential confounding or mediating variables are adjusted for, the values of causal effects can be estimated using standard statistical modelling techniques (e.g. linear regression). The initial causal network can be specified either through expert knowledge of known causal mechanisms (e.g. through expert elicitation or literature review) or automated Causal Discovery methods such as PCMCI (Runge et al., 2019). It is currently unclear how robust automated Causal Discovery methods are for weather and climate analysis, particularly where the relationships are seasonally-varying or non-stationary, so in this context expert elicitation is the preferred approach.

2.2 Exploration of relationships between large-scale drivers and weather patterns

WP classifications can be used to characterize the broad-scale atmospheric circulation for a given region and timescale (Richardson et al., 2018). Different WPs can be associated with statistical distributions of weather variables, such as temperature, precipitation and wind speed. In fact, certain WPs can be closely linked to hazards such as fluvial or coastal flooding, with forecasting tools (e.g. Neal et al., 2018; Richardson et al., 2020) developed to exploit these relationships. This suggests that, if associations and causal relationships can be found between large-scale drivers and WPs, the WPs could be used as an explanatory link between large-scale drivers and compound events.

Having identified a set of relevant large-scale drivers, the next step of the COMPASS framework is to explore the relationships between these drivers and the different WPs which characterize atmospheric circulation for the region of interest. For the example of compound flooding in the UK, the set of 30 WPs defined by Neal et al. (2016) could be used. Statistical testing of correlation or association coefficients (e.g. point biserial correlation) can be used to identify any statistically significant relationships. The data and analysis used for this step of the framework could be applicable to other compound events affecting the UK in winter, such as compound wind and rain extremes (e.g. Manning et al., 2024).

2.3 Assessment of stationarity of weather patterns

The stationarity of WPs is a key assumption in many studies. In the past and present climate, stationarity of WPs (i.e. in terms of their spatial characteristics at different times) is assumed for the development of forecasting tools and identifying high risk WPs for particular impacts. Looking to future climate, studies including those by Pope et al. (2022) and Perks et al. (2023) have linked changes in frequency of impactful weather patterns to changes in hazards in a future climate. If the characteristics of a canonical WP are expected to change in a future climate, then this would imply differences in the impacts associated with them. The same principles would apply when considering impacts linked to WPs in the context of attribution (i.e. steps 4-5 of Figure 2). The stationarity of WPs (or lack of it) is also important when linking large-scale drivers to WPs, with any long-term changes or higher frequency variability in the spatial characteristics of WPs expected to have implications on the interpretation of results. Therefore, the next step of the framework is to develop

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

an understanding of any temporal change in WP characteristics within the broader context of a changing climate or climate variability.

Temporal changes in characteristics of WPs can be assessed using a range of methods. One possible method is frequency analysis, for example by assessing changes in the annual occurrence of each WP over time. Alternatively, clustering based analysis could be used, whereby WPs are re-generated for different time periods and compared to the canonical WPs using a goodness of fit metric to assess spatial changes. Finally, time series analysis could be applied to daily goodness of fit metrics measuring how well historical daily patterns match to the canonical WPs.

2.4 Exploration of relationships between weather patterns and compound events

To continue linking large-scale drivers to compound events, the next step of the COMPASS framework is to explore the relationship between WPs and compound events. Depending on the compound event of interest, there may already be research linking the compound event (or one or more of the constituent single hazards) to certain WPs. For the UK, for example, several studies have explored the relationship between the 30 WPs of Neal et al. (2016) and a range of univariate hazards and compound events. In this case, it is possible to review the literature and combine information from various sources, to identify a set of key WPs which are related to the compound event of interest. This is the approach demonstrated later in this report, as the hazards related to the case study (Section 7) have previously been studied for the UK.

For other compound events, such as those which have not been studied to the same extent or require greater specificity, or those affecting regions outside of the UK, this step would require additional analysis. Following similar methods to those in the literature (e.g. Neal et al., 2018; Richardson et al., 2020), conditional distributions of the hazard(s) or representative metric(s) of interest could be derived, given the occurrence of each of a set of WPs. If there are known impactful thresholds of the hazards, the probability of exceeding them given the occurrence of a WP could also be calculated.

For example, a compound flooding event could be defined as a period of 1-day where both the rainfall in a catchment and the skew surge at the nearby coast exceed their 95th percentiles at that time of year (noting as per Hendry et al. (2021) that not all contributing hazards necessarily need to exceed a threshold for a multivariate compound flooding event to occur), The exceedance probability for each of the WPs could then be calculated. This would facilitate the identification of WPs where there is an increased probability of exceedance, and therefore an increased likelihood of a compound flooding event occurring. This method could be used to select one or more focus WPs which can be taken forwards to the next step.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

2.5 Identification of focus weather patterns

In addition to general analysis of relationships between a set of WPs and certain types of compound event (as described in Section 2.4), the next step of the COMPASS framework is to identify WPs to focus on for further analysis. These focus WPs are a small number of WPs (e.g. 1-3 different patterns) which are found to show particularly strong links to the compound event of interest and can be incorporated into a case study as outlined in Section 2.6.

The method used to identify focus WPs for a compound event will depend on the event characteristics. If the compound event is a multivariate event, with all contributing hazards occurring on a single day, then the most logical WP to focus on is simply the WP which was assigned to that day. However, for some multivariate or spatially compounding events, or by definition temporally compounding or pre-conditioned events the regional atmospheric circulation patterns leading to the compound event may be less clear. In this scenario, bespoke analysis would be required to identify the WPs which best capture the circulation patterns leading to the event. For example, the most frequent WPs occurring over the time period of interest (e.g. a season) could be identified. Alternatively, the most frequent WPs occurring on the days which contribute the most to the hazards (i.e. the hottest/wettest/driest days) could be identified, similar to the method implemented for case studies by (Richardson et al., 2020).

2.65 Estimating causal effects of large-scale drivers on focus WPs

After identifying the WPs which are linked to the compound event of interest (described in Section 2.5, or step 5 of the framework) and conducting initial analysis of their relationship with large-scale drivers in (described in Section 2.2, or step 2 of the framework), the causality of these relationships should now be assessed as the next step of the framework. By extending the causal network between the large-scale drivers to the WPs of interest, it is possible to assess whether there is a causal link between them. For example, within a season the frequency of occurrence of a specific WP might be linked to the large-scale drivers, such as the frequency of WP 29 (deep low-pressure system located west of Ireland) of the MO30 occurring more frequently under a winter with a strongly negative North Atlantic Oscillation. Once the causal effect of any large-scale drivers which are found not to be conditionally independent from the frequency of a WP has been isolated, it is possible to predict the number of days which are expected to be assigned to a specific WP, given the values of the large-scale drivers for that year. If a particularly strong causal relationship is found, it may be possible to compare a counter-factual scenario (where the large-scale drivers took different values) to the factual scenario (the one which was observed).

2.76 Quantifying the impact of large-scale drivers on compound events

Depending on the causal strength of the relationship between large-scale drivers and the WPs, and the WPs and the occurrence of compound events, it may be possible to make statements about the impact of the large-

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

scale drivers on the compound event itself, proceeding to the final step of the COMPASS framework. There are a number of ways that an understanding of large-scale drivers and WPs linked to compound events can benefit climate change attribution studies. Although this stage of the framework has not been applied in this report, in this section we describe the possible applications.

Attribution of compound events often requires very large ensembles from climate models, (which are expensive to produce and analyse) therefore conditional attribution methods (such as analogue approaches) can be advantageous in such scenarios. Conditional attribution requires an understanding of the large-scale drivers of the compound event, with the possibility of selecting analogues (events with similar synoptic circulation patterns but taken from counterfactual climate datasets, as demonstrated by Noyelle et al. (2025)) based on WPs or large-scale drivers that are demonstrated to increase the chance of compound impacts.

Furthermore, attribution studies have shown different strengths in results based on the level of conditionality (whether statistics are conditioned on the dynamical state of the climate system in addition to the climate change scenario, e.g. Buschow et al. (2024)) meaning that it is important to consider both conditional and unconditional methods. Whether conditional or not, a strong understanding of the large-scale drivers of an event provides helpful context to the attribution results. It can also support the model validation stage of an attribution study, to assess whether the large-scale drivers most relevant to the event are well represented in the climate model data being used.

Finally, understanding how the large-scale drivers of a compound event are changing can be key to understanding the relative contributions of thermodynamic and large-scale dynamic changes to the overall change in probability of the event.

To operationalise the COMPASS framework described above, we require a dataset that links large-scale drivers with weather patterns. Such a dataset allows us to test whether certain drivers are associated with particular circulation regimes, whether these relationships are stable over time, and ultimately whether they can be used to explain the likelihood of compound events. Chapter 3 introduces the dataset that underpins the remainder of this report, providing the foundation for the analyses in Chapters 4–6 and the case study in Chapter 7.

3. Applying the COMPASS Framework: Dataset for linking large-scale drivers and weather patterns in the UK

This chapter presents the dataset foundation for the framework. We have produced a dataset linking large-scale drivers with daily classifications of UK weather patterns (MO30) into a single resource, with a particular focus on UK winters. This dataset represents steps 1 and 2 of the COMPASS framework and facilitates the remaining steps. It is designed to enable the COMPASS framework to be applied in practice: in Chapter 4, we use it to explore relationships between drivers and weather patterns; in Chapter 5, to explore assessing the stationarity of these patterns; in Chapter 6, to examine how weather patterns link to hazards; and in Chapter 7, to demonstrate the framework in a real-world case study. While the dataset is described in detail here, its primary role is to provide the backbone for the analyses that follow.

The dataset is used for analysis in this report, to apply the framework for a particular case study, but is also made available for other WPs of the COMPASS project and the wider research community.

3.1. Data

This dataset combines two existing datasets, the first of which represent a set of large-scale drivers (Sexton, 2024) and the second of which represents UK WPs (Neal et al., 2016).

3.1.1. Large scale drivers

To represent the historical values of large-scale drivers which research has previously identified as being relevant for UK circulation, we use a set of variables provided by Sexton (2024), following the definitions given in Table 1. Although Sexton (2024) provide these driver variables for a set of climate model simulations, here we only use the monthly data calculated from the ERA5 Reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2020) between 1959 and 2021 as this report is focused on understanding historical relationships.

Pre-processing

Sexton et al. (2025) calculated monthly driver values for each variable, before aggregating over seasons (e.g. calculating a time series of January-February average NAO values from monthly average NAO values). Each variable was first standardised using its mean and standard deviation from the ERA5 reanalysis, and then detrended. The detrending is to remove long-term trends which can cause spurious correlations due to issues with collinearity. Sexton et al. (2025) found that in practice, this only made a difference for Barents-Kara Sea Ice Concentration (BKSIC; due to more sea ice melt under climate change), and a very small difference for NAO (where there is a small positive trend).

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

In this work, we use both monthly and annual (seasonally aggregated) driver time series, both of which are standardised using the series' mean and standard deviation. The standardised time series are linearly detrended, except for BKSIC where we instead apply a 30-year high pass filter to retain interannual variability.

Table 1: Summary of climate drivers calculated by Sexton et al. (2025)Sexton et al. (2025)Sexton et al. (2025)Sexton et al. (2025). ERA5 data covers Jan 1959-Dec 2021. Throughout the report, drivers are referred to using the driver name acronyms from the first column.

Driver name	Season	Definition	Description
North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO)	January-February (JF)	Difference of Mean Sea Level Pressure (MSLP): Azores region 28.5-20° W, 36-40° N minus Iceland region 25-16.5° W, 63.5-70° N.	Late winter NAO index
El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO)	August-September-October (ASO)	Niño 3.4 index. Average of sea surface temperature over 170-120°W, 5°S-5°N.	Early season ENSO
Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD)	October-November-December (OND)	Difference of surface temperature: average of 50-70° E, 10° S-10° N minus average of 90-110° E, 10° S-0° N.	IOD
Barents Kara Sea Ice Concentration (BKSIC)	OND	Average of sea ice fraction over 19-100°E, 65-85°N.	Sea ice fraction across Barents and Kara seas
Quasi-biennial oscillation (QBO)	December-January-February (DJF)	Zonal average of eastward wind speed at 30 hPa between 5° S-5° N.	QBO
Stratospheric Polar Vortex (SPV)	DJF	Zonal average of eastward wind speed at 10 hPa between 60° N and 75° N.	SPV

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Atlantic Jet (AtlJet)	DJF	Average of eastward wind speed at 850 hPa over 100- 70° W, 20-35° N.	Part of southwest North Atlantic jet that is affected by Pacific Jet
Aleutian Low (AleutLow)	DJF	Average of MSLP over 175-140° W, 35-55° N.	Region with greatest variance of MSLP in the Aleutian Low.
Atlantic Dipole (AtlDip)	DJF	Difference in sea surface temperature (SST): Average of 70-40° W, 22-35° N minus average of 60-5° W, 10° S-10° N.	Strength of SST dipole that linearly affects NAO
Urals MSLP (UralsMSLP)	September October November (SON)	Average of MSLP over 40-85° E, 45-70° N.	MSLP over the Urals

3.1.2. Weather Patterns

To represent weather types relevant to the UK, we utilise the well-established MO30 WPs (Neal et al., 2016). The set of 30 WPs were derived objectively through k-means clustering of daily mean sea level pressure data (1850-2003) from European and North Atlantic Daily to Multi-decadal Climate Variability (EMULATE) MSLP (EMSLP) data (Ansell et al., 2006). This provides an assignment of one of the 30 WPs to each day from 1850 onwards, with WPs from 2004 onwards assigned by applying the clustering definitions to mean sea level pressure data from ERA5 (Hersbach et al., 2020). The definitions for the 30 WPs are shown in Figure 3.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 3: Definitions for the set of 30 weather patterns. Mean sea level pressure (MSLP) anomalies plotted as filled contours (hPa) and MSLP mean values plotted in foreground (2 hPa intervals). Figure taken from Neal et al. (2016).

The final set of 30 weather patterns were derived following an iterative process, with each set of patterns evaluated by operational meteorologists to ensure that the full range of atmospheric circulation types affecting the UK and surrounding European area were adequately represented (Neal et al., 2016). The 30 patterns are primarily intended for use in medium-range forecasting (out to 15 days), where each day in the forecast could be assigned to one of the 30 patterns (Neal et al., 2016). These can be used to examine variations of a broadscale pattern, such as variations within a cyclonic westerly (e.g. distinguishing between WP 10 – a calm westerly circulation pattern – and WP 20 – a stormy westerly circulation pattern)⁴.

⁴ <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/research/news/2016/new-weather-patterns-for-uk-and-europe> Last accessed: 28/08/2025.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

At the seasonal timescale (i.e. more than one month ahead), only a broad indication of atmospheric circulation is possible from a forecast, so a smaller set of WPs were derived from the original set of 30— using the same EMSLP and ERA5 data – to be used for long-range and seasonal forecasts (Neal et al., 2016). To enable seamless comparisons with the original set of patterns at intermediate timescales, the reduced set of patterns was produced objectively by merging patterns with the highest spatially correlated pattern centroids from the original set of 30 until a final reduced set of eight WPs was selected. The definitions for the eight WPs are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Composites for the eight weather patterns. Numbers in brackets show the sub-patterns from the set of 30 used to form the new composites. Mean sea level pressure (MSLP) anomalies plotted as filled contours (hPa) and MSLP mean values plotted in foreground (2 hPa intervals). Figure taken from Neal et al. (2016).

Both the sets of 30 and eight WPs are numbered according to their annual historic occurrences between 1850 and 2003 (the period used to generate the patterns; Neal et al., 2016). For the set of 30, WP 1 occurs most often annually (around 6.5% of the time) and WP 30 occurs least often annually (around 1.5% of the time)⁴. Clustering MSLP anomalies tends to group days with strong anomalies as well as days with weak anomalies, resulting in some interesting seasonality; for the set of 30 WPs, lower numbered patterns have weaker MSLP anomalies and tend to occur more in summer, whilst higher numbered patterns have stronger MSLP anomalies and tend to occur more in winter (Neal et al., 2016). Understanding this climatological variability in WP occurrence throughout the year helps identify more unusual patterns at certain times of year, which can sometimes be an indication of severe weather (e.g. the occurrence of WP 30 in summer; Neal et al., 2016).

Seasonality is less evident with the eight patterns because their derivation combines patterns from the original set which have varying MSLP anomaly intensities, however the anomaly features in sub-patterns are generally in the same place (Neal et al., 2016). Table 2 describes 8 WPs and their percentage occurrence in the EMSL data (1850-2003).

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Table 2: Descriptions of the eight WPs and percentage occurrences from the EMSL data (1850–2003), taken from Neal et al. (2016) Neal et al. (2016) Neal et al. (2016) Neal et al. (2016) and Neal et al. (2024). Pattern names and descriptions are relevant to the UK.

WP	Description	Sub-patterns	Percentage occurrence (1 dp)
1. NAO–	All sub-patterns going into this type in general have positive MSLP anomalies to the north of the UK and negative MSLP anomalies to the south of the UK, resulting in a negative NAO pattern.	6, 9, 11, 19, 25, 27, 28	21.2
2. NAO+	All sub-patterns going into this type in general have negative MSLP anomalies to the north of the UK and positive MSLP anomalies to the south of the UK, resulting in a zonal (positive NAO) pattern.	4, 8, 20, 23, 26, 30	17.8
3. Northwesterly	All sub-patterns going into this type in general have negative MSLP anomalies to the northeast of the UK and positive MSLP anomalies to the southwest of the UK, resulting in a north-westerly flow. Sub-patterns going into this type vary between being cyclonic and anticyclonic, but the direction of flow is the same.	1, 13, 14, 24	15.0
4. Southwesterly	All sub-patterns going into this type in general have negative MSLP anomalies to the northwest of the UK and positive MSLP anomalies to the southeast of the UK, resulting in a southwesterly flow. Sub-patterns going into this type vary between being cyclonic and anticyclonic but the direction of flow is the same.	2, 12, 15, 21	14.8
5. Scandinavian high	All sub-patterns going into this type in general have negative MSLP anomalies to the west of the UK and positive MSLP anomalies to the east of the UK, resulting in a south to south easterly flow. Most sub-patterns in this type are anticyclonic.	5, 16, 17, 22	12.4
6. High pressure centred over UK.	Both sub-patterns going into this type have positive MSLP anomalies over the UK and to the south of the UK, with weak negative MSLP anomalies to the north of the UK. This results in an anticyclonic westerly or southwesterly flow.	3, 18	7.9
7. Low close to UK	Both sub-patterns going into this type extend a trough over the UK. Negative MSLP anomalies are centred just to the west of the UK resulting in a cyclonic southwesterly flow.	7, 29	6.5
8. Azores high	Only one pattern goes into this type which shows an anticyclonic westerly flow over the UK, with an Azores high extension.	10	4.3

3.2. Method

There are several possible methods for temporally linking the large-scale driver dataset to the WPs. Consider a hypothetical large-scale driver which has an almost immediate effect on circulation patterns in the UK: we would want to link the values of a large-scale driver on a given day to the assigned MO30 WP on that same day. In practice, large-scale drivers are not expected to vary greatly at a daily frequency, and they tend to be quantified by monthly or seasonal aggregations (as in Sexton et al. (2025)). As such, we link the values of a large-scale driver on a given month to the assigned MO30 WPs for each day within that month (thus repeating the large-scale driver values 28-31 times depending on the number of days in the month).

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

It is also possible that there is a greater time lag between a large-scale driver value and its effect on circulation in the UK. To assess this, a dataset would need to link values of the large-scale driver in the relevant months (i.e. a season-aggregated value) to the assigned MO30 WPs in the target month(s). Taking a naïve approach, there would be an overwhelming number of possible combinations of months of which to aggregate a set of large-scale drivers over to explore their relationship with WPs. However, Sexton et al. (2025) show how expert elicitation can be used to reduce the number of possible combinations and construct a causal network between large-scale drivers which are relevant for UK winter circulation. For our dataset, we are therefore able to incorporate the insights from Sexton et al. (2025)'s causal network and link the UK WPs to the set of season-aggregated large-scale drivers listed in Table 1. If constructing a similar causal network relevant for circulation in a different region where expert knowledge exists, a similar approach could be taken. If expert knowledge does not already exist, then further exploration would be required.

Whether linking monthly or season-aggregated values of large-scale drivers to MO30 WPs, we end up with a one-to-many relationship where each large-scale driver value is repeated for each of the associated MO30 assigned days. Whilst this data structure is helpful when considering a specific historical day, when one might wish to look up both the MO30 WP and large-scale driver values, it complicates predictive or causal analysis, where each MO30 WP “observation” within a month/season is likely to invalidate assumptions of temporal independence. Therefore, we further aggregate the data by calculating monthly/seasonal frequencies and proportions of each MO30 WP, thus retaining a one-to-one relationship between large-scale driver values and MO30 WP assignments. This enables the exploration of relationships between a large-scale driver in a particular month or year, and the number of days in the target month/season which are assigned to a specific WP.

The dataset D3.3⁵ contains multiple CSV files, each linking the same set of large-scale drivers to WPs (from both the 30 and 8 classifications) using a different combination of the pre-processing, temporal-linking and aggregation methods described above. Table 3 provides a summary of the methods applied to each of the CSV files.

Table 3: Information about the methods applied to each of the files comprising D3.3.

File Name	De-trended	Temporal frequency of large-scale driver	Aggregated weather types
monthly_era5_driver_wp.csv	No	Monthly	No
monthly_era5_driver_wp_detrend.csv	Yes	Monthly	No
annual_era5_driver_wp.csv	No	Annual/seasonal	No
annual_era5_driver_wp_detrend.csv	Yes	Annual/seasonal	No
proportion_era5_driver_wp.csv	No	Annual/seasonal	Yes

⁵ Dataset on weather types and largescale climate drivers: 10.5281/zenodo.16984885.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

proportion_era5_driver_wp_detrend.csv	Yes	Annual/seasonal	Yes
---------------------------------------	-----	-----------------	-----

For more information about the dataset, see D3.3.

4. Large-scale drivers and weather patterns

This section presents the results obtained by applying step 2 from the COMPASS framework in Figure 2 to the dataset described in Section 3, to explore relationships between the MO30 WPs and large-scale drivers relevant for UK winter circulation.

Figure 5 shows a time series of standardised JF NAO between 1961 and 2021, both before and after applying the de-trending step. It also shows horizontal box and whisker plots displaying the distribution of JF NAO values which coincide with the assignment of each of the MO30 WPs. Figure 6 shows the equivalent for the OND BKSIC, with the equivalent plots for the other drivers in the dataset shown in Annex A (Section 11). These figures show that, similar to the findings of Sexton et al. (2025), de-trending has little effect on the large-scale driver values with the exception of OND BKSIC which is heavily impacted by climate change. For consistency with Sexton et al (2024), we use the de-trended version of the large-scale drivers in the remainder of our analysis, noting that this should have negligible impacts on the results for most of the drivers except OND BKSIC.

Visually examining the box and whisker plots, there does not appear to be a strong association between the driver values occurring with each of the MO30 WPs. In the case of DJF QBO (shown in Figure), for example, it appears that any of the WPs can occur with almost any driver value, with the whiskers on the boxplot extending across nearly the full range of DJF QBO values. There are small shifts in the median and interquartile range of the QBO values depending on the WP; however, we cannot say at this stage whether this shows a significant association. For JF NAO, meanwhile, in Figure x there is an indication of a relationship with the WPs – there are WPs (e.g. 7, 27, and 29) which have never occurred in January or February when the standardised, de-trended JF NAO value has been above 1. Further analysis is required, however, to assess the significance of this possible association.

To explore the statistical association between the large-scale drivers and the 30 WPs, measures of both global and local association are assessed using the R package “descriptio”(Robette, 2024). Global association measures the strength of the relationship between a large-scale driver and the set of WPs as a whole. We use the square of the correlation ratio (eta squared; the weighted variance of the large-scale driver mean value for each WP, divided by the variance of all large-scale driver values). This is a measure intended for relationships between categorical and numerical variables. In this case it expresses the proportion of the variance of the large-scale driver value which is “explained” by the WP assignment, and it varies between 0 and 1. The significance of eta squared is assessed using a permutation test, a form of combinatorial inference. If the p-

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

value of this permutation test is less than a selected significance level (e.g. 0.05), then the null hypothesis (of no relationship between the two variables) can be rejected, allowing us to draw conclusions about the statistical significance of relationships between a large-scale driver and the set of 30 WPs.

In this work, it is more useful to consider the local association (the association between a large-scale driver and a specific WP) as this would allow us to assess the statistical significance of relationships between a focus WP and a large-scale driver (thus identifying large-scale drivers to potentially incorporate into our causal network). For local association, the point biserial correlation and test statistic from Lebart et al. (1984) are used. The point biserial correlation measures the magnitude of the difference between the means of the large-scale driver depending on whether the observation is assigned to each WP or not. The correlation varies between -1 and 1, with an absolute value of 0 indicating no association and an absolute value of 1 indicating a perfect association. A positive value indicating a positive association and a negative value indicating a negative association. The significance of the local association is assessed using the test statistic from Lebart et al. (1984) – the null hypothesis of there being no association between the driver and the WP can be rejected at a selected significance level (e.g. 0.05) if the test statistic's p-value is less than this level.

Figure 7 shows the point biserial correlation for the local association between the DJF AtlJet and each of the 30 WPs (x-axis) with the significance level of Lebart et al. (1984)'s p-value for the test statistic shown by the different shades of blue. Rejection at a smaller significance level is shown in a darker shade of blue. The p-value for the global association test, based on eta squared, is shown above the plot. Figure 8-Figure 12 show the equivalent for the other large-scale drivers in the dataset.

At the $\alpha=0.05$ significance level, we find that there is a significant global association between the WPs and all the large-scale drivers which were tested. Additionally, we find a significant local association between some (differing) WPs and each of the large-scale drivers. For the JF NAO for example, almost all the WPs show a significant local association. For some other drivers, such as the OND BKSIC, there are much fewer WPs which are significantly associated with the driver, with only WPs 6, 7, 20, 27, 28, and 29 being highlighted. These figures also provide information about the direction of the local associations. A summary of these results is given in Table 4.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 5: Plots showing time series of standardised JF NAO before (a) and after (b) de-trending, and box and whisker plots of standardised JF NAO corresponding to days assigned to each of the MO30 WPs (c). The lower, middle, and upper hinges of the boxplots show the 25th, 50th (median), and 75th percentiles of each distribution respectively, with the whiskers extending to the largest/smallest value no further than 1.5 times the Inter-Quartile Range (IQR) from the hinge and data beyond the end of the whiskers plotted individually.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 6: Plots showing time series of standardised OND Barents Kara Sea Ice Concentration before (a) and after (b) de-trending, and box and whisker plots of standardised OND Barents Kara Sea Ice Concentration corresponding to days assigned to each of the MO30 WPs (c). The lower, middle, and upper hinges of the boxplots show the 25th, 50th (median), and 75th percentiles of each distribution respectively, with the whiskers extending to the largest/smallest value no further than 1.5 times the IQR from the hinge and data beyond the end of the whiskers plotted individually.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 7: Bar plot showing the test statistic values for association between DJF Atlantic Jet and the assignment of the MO30 WPs in JF, with the significance level of these statistics shown in shades of blue.

Figure 8: Bar plot showing the test statistic values for association between DJF Aleutian Low and the assignment of the MO30 WPs in JF, with the significance level of these statistics shown in shades of blue.

Figure 9: Bar plot showing the test statistic values for association between DJF Atlantic Dipole and the assignment of the MO30 WPs in JF, with the significance level of these statistics shown in shades of blue.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 10: Bar plot showing the test statistic values for association between OND Barents Kara Sea Ice Concentration and the assignment of the MO30 WPs in JF, with the significance level of these statistics shown in shades of blue.

Figure 11: Bar plot showing the test statistic values for association between ASO El Niño Southern Oscillation and the assignment of the MO30 WPs in JF, with the significance level of these statistics shown in shades of blue.

Figure 12: Bar plot showing the test statistic values for association between OND Indian Ocean Dipole and the assignment of the MO30 WPs in JF, with the significance level of these statistics shown in shades of blue.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 13: Bar plot showing the test statistic values for association between JF NAO and the assignment of the MO30 WPs in JF, with the significance level of these statistics shown in shades of blue.

Figure 14: Bar plot showing the test statistic values for association between DJF Quasi-Biennial Oscillation and the assignment of the MO30 WPs in JF, with the significance level of these statistics shown in shades of blue.

Figure 15: Bar plot showing the test statistic values for association between DJF Stratospheric Polar Vortex and the assignment of the MO30 WPs in JF, with the significance level of these statistics shown in shades of blue.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 16: Bar plot showing the test statistic values for association between SON Urals Mean Sea Level Pressure and the assignment of the MO30 WPs in JF, with the significance level of these statistics shown in shades of blue.

Table 4: Summary of the WPs found to have significant (at the level $p < 0.05$) positive or negative local association with each large-scale driver.

Large-scale driver	WPs with significant positive association	WPs with significant negative association
DJF AtlJet	7, 9, 11, 24, 27, 28, 29	15, 18, 20, 23, 26, 30
DJF AtleutLow	2, 16, 30	11, 14, 19, 27
DJF AtlDip	10, 11, 24, 30	22, 25, 27, 28
OND BKSIC	6, 9, 29	16, 20, 27, 28
ASO ENSO	9, 19, 24, 29	20, 21
OND IOD	4, 23, 28, 29, 30	12, 17, 27
JF NAO	10, 13, 15, 18, 20, 21, 23, 26, 30	7, 9, 11, 16, 19, 22, 24, 25, 27, 28, 29
DJF QBO	4, 13, 25, 30	11, 17, 27, 28, 29
DJF SPV	15, 20, 23, 25, 26, 30	7, 9, 11, 14, 16, 17, 24, 27, 28, 29
SON UralsMSLP	7, 11, 16, 19, 28	20, 23, 26, 29

In addition to exploring the relationships between WP assignments on individual days and the large-scale drivers, we also explore the relationship with the frequency of WP assignments across a whole season. For each of the large-scale drivers, we look at the frequency of selected WPs being assigned against the value of the large-scale driver. Figure 17 shows scatterplots of the frequency of each WP (one per facet) against the values of the JF NAO. The equivalent plots for the other large-scale drivers are shown in Annex A (Section 11).

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

First noting that some of the 30 WPs rarely occur in winter (e.g. WP 1 has never occurred more than 10 times within one JF season, using JF as this these are the target months used by Sexton et al (2024)), we explore whether there appears to be a link between the number of times a WP occurs in a season and the value of a large-scale driver occurring before or during that season. For some of the large-scale drivers, including BKSIC and UralsMSLP, there does not seem to be an obvious relationship, with seasons of more frequent occurrences of certain WPs not being linked to years of particularly high or low large-scale driver values. In other cases, for example JF NAO and SPV it appears there may be a link with some of the years with higher counts of WPs like 27 and 30 occurring with higher or lower values of the drivers.

The findings from this section indicate that there is an association between the large-scale drivers NAO, and North Atlantic WPs in January and February. Specifically, there is a significant association between large-scale drivers (NAO, ENSO, IOD, BKSIC, QBO, SPV, AtlJet, AleutLow, AtlDip, and UralsMSLP) and several of the WPs from Neal et al (2016). There are also possible links between the frequency of occurrence of certain WPs and the large-scale drivers, indicating potential to assess the significance of these links for specific WPs of interest which are linked to compound events. It will be important to assess the interactions and potential confounding effects between these drivers and the occurrence of WPs, with causal inference offering a method for accounting for these and estimating the strength of causal relationships between the network of large-scale drivers as a whole.

The methods applied in this section can be used for any set of distinct WPs and large-scale driver values, representing a statistically justified method to assess the association between a categorical and continuous variable.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 17: Scatterplots showing the frequency of a given MO30 WP in January and February of each year, against the JF NAO of the same year, with each WP shown by a different plot facet.

5. Stationarity of weather patterns

5.1. Stationarity

WPs characterising atmospheric circulation are a key part of the proposed framework for understanding and quantifying the influence of large-scale drivers on compound events. WPs are being used to bridge the gap between large-scale drivers and compound events, as they can be linked to both. Therefore, it is important to test the assumption that these WPs are stationary in their spatial variability (i.e. not changing their spatial structure) and temporal variability (i.e. not changing their occurrence frequency) so that they can serve as reliable conditional constraints in likelihood calculations. There is already evidence of changes in WP frequency over time (Richardson et al., 2018), and so here we are looking to understand how the spatial patterns may have changed over time.

This work begins to explore WP stationarity by using a clustering-based pattern comparison method to see how patterns differ between different time windows. The problem of assessing spatial stationarity is a complex one and, while this method makes progress in addressing the problem, it is important to state that it is currently not possible to distinguish between true non-stationarity, and differences in weather pattern morphology due to artefacts of methodological constraints (e.g. changing frequency of weather patterns, k-means decision boundary being unstable, etc).

For the purposes of this report, it is not yet clear how to define statistically significant changes in WP morphology. For that reason, this work aims to identify any persistent or notable changes in the spatial structure or intensity of atmospheric circulation patterns from the canonical atmospheric circulation patterns (or other representative set), which informs our understanding of what non-stationarity could look like. This work helps to understand what is considered a notable change from typical morphological WP ranges, what time scales these changes may be occurring at, and the key challenges and uncertainties faced when looking to assess stationarity.

5.2. Methodology

A brief overview of the method and the main challenge it presents follows, with a more comprehensive description of the method in section 5.3. Configuration. The established method for assessing spatial WP changes between time windows uses k-means clustering (Philipp et al., 2007) on dimensionally reduced daily-mean MSLP ERA5 reanalysis data (Hersbach et al., 2020), across multiple time windows, where the seasonal cycle has been removed. The resultant weather patterns (the cluster centroids) are assigned to patterns in a chosen reference window using the 'Decider' distance measure (Neal et al., 2016). Where the distance measure provides a common basis for comparing changes across different windows. The statistics across time windows are then visualised to assess spatial WP changes over the historical period. In theory, this approach can be applied to WPs for any domain, but here we focus on the UK and surrounding European area. The main

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

challenge with this approach has been reducing the inherent variability in the clustering method due to the stochastic nature of the k-means algorithm, which makes assessment extremely difficult. Whilst a robust process appears to have been established, hinting at a degree of non-stationarity, the method has been refined to reduce variability.

Dimensionality reduction of the MSLP data highlights the difficulties in reducing the variability in the clustering method. Here we examine dimensionality reduction for the daily-mean MSLP ERA5 data for years 1979-1994 (which will be the first window in our series of time windows). Principal Component Analysis (PCA) (Pearson, 1901) has been used to reduce the dimensionality of the data from over 28,000 MSLP grid points to 2 principal components (dimensions) prior to clustering to improve the efficiency and consistency of WPs generated with k-means (Figure 18, left). Alternative dimensionality reduction techniques have been explored to demonstrate the difficulty in generating consistent cluster definitions and to try and produce more distinct patterns whilst preserving local and global structure, e.g. preserving the relative distances of neighbouring points and points that are further away (Wang et al., 2021). The dimensionality reduction techniques considered are UMAP, T-SNE, TriMap, and PacMap (Amid & Warmuth, 2022; Garry & Palmer, 2025; McInnes et al., 2020; van der Maaten & Hinton, 2008; Wang et al., 2021). When reducing to 2 dimensions, almost all these methods improve cluster definition and separation, with reduced similarity between clusters, when compared to PCA. PacMap showed the best improvement on PCA; an example of the output for PacMap is shown next to the output for PCA in Figure 18. However, unlike PCA, these methods are non-deterministic which adds to the variability in the clusters produced. To assess stationarity the method needs to be as deterministic as possible to reduce uncertainty, and the consistency of patterns was not found to be sufficient using these techniques.

Figure 18: Two-dimensional output of PCA (left) and PacMap (right) for ERA5 daily-mean MSLP data 1979-1994. The k-means assigned clusters are labelled and colour coded.

Revisiting PCA, as the only deterministic technique tested so far, it was found that using 2 components only explains ~60% of the variance in the data. To explain at least 90% of the variance, 6 or more components are required (Figure 19). However, for this dataset, using more components worsens cluster separation and makes

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

clusters more similar. This was determined from calculating Silhouette scores, where a higher score indicates well defined and well separated clusters and from Davies–Bouldin scores, where a lower score indicates less similarity between clusters. The optimal choice is 6 components, which should produce more representative WPs and should not add to the variability when clustering.

Figure 19: The cumulative explained variance of the daily-mean MSLP data for the first 30 principal components, the 90% variance threshold is indicated by the dotted line.

5.3. Configuration

The final setup uses the established k-means clustering configuration with k-means++ initialisation, 1000 maximum iterations, and 20 random re-initialisations. The dataset used is the daily-mean MSLP ERA5 dataset 1979-2025 (Hersbach et al., 2020). The domain used is that of the MO30 canonical Decider patterns, covering the UK and surrounding European area (Neal et al., 2016). From this data, for each time window, the daily climatology (calculated from 1979-2010 day of year averages) is subtracted to obtain anomalies, which are then weighted by grid cell area, and normalised to the range 0-1. The MSLP data are then reshaped from a 3D array of shape (days × latitudes × longitudes) into a 2D array of shape (days × grid points), and its spatial dimensionality is then reduced to 6 components using PCA. Sets of 8 and 30 WPs are generated in this way for 32 moving windows of 15-year duration, incremented by 1-year through the period 1979-2010, e.g. the first window spans the range 1979-1993 inclusive, the second window 1980-1994 and so on. The 15-year window duration was chosen to capture natural variability in the climate and minimising the overlap between time windows. This clustering process is performed in parallel, utilising multiprocessing. The generated patterns for each window are then assigned one-to-one to a chosen reference window. The sets of canonical Decider patterns (Figure 3 and Figure 4) and the first window of generated patterns are both used as reference windows to aid analysis. The canonical patterns are re-gridded from the lower resolution EMSLP dataset grid

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

(Ansell et al., 2006) to the higher resolution ERA5 grid to allow assignment. The pattern assignment calculates the Decider distance, the area weighted grid-point average sum-of-squares difference (Neal et al., 2016), between each pattern in a time window and each pattern in the reference window. For pressure data in hPa, the units of the distance are thus hPa^2 . A smaller distance corresponds to a better fit to the reference pattern features in terms of intensity, though there is unlikely to be a perfect match due to variations inside each pattern. The assignment process then solves the linear sum assignment problem (LSAP) using a modified Jonker-Volgenant algorithm (Crouse, 2016; Virtanen et al., 2020) to optimally assign the patterns, finding the best combination of one-to-one matches with the reference patterns and minimising the total distance metric for a window. The assigned patterns are then plotted on a heatmap to assess whether the frequency of occurrence of the reference patterns has changed over time, and the associated distances are plotted on a stacked area plot. The distances for each WP are plotted separately as line plots for evaluating individual WP trends. To aid in analysis, additional pattern statistics for Pearson correlation coefficients (with assigned reference patterns), frequency of occurrence (in the time window), and persistence (the average span of days with this pattern in the time window) have also been produced.

5.4. Sources of uncertainty

There are several expected sources of uncertainty and increased distance (regardless of any non-stationarity) when assigning patterns which prevent any perfect matches and generally distort assessment. Firstly, the difference in grid resolution. The low spatial resolution of the canonical patterns means that, despite re-gridding, the fine detail in some of the pressure patterns is not captured as well as the patterns generated from ERA5. Secondly, there is uncertainty in the fact that comparing WPs is comparing k-means cluster centroids. The centroid is an average of the members of the cluster and so obtaining the exact same centroid when using data from different time windows is unlikely. The high density of the daily MSLP data, with ambiguous local and global structures, makes selecting well-defined clusters and centroids objectively difficult. Finally, a source of increased distance when comparing to the 8 canonical patterns comes from the method of generation, where from the MO30 canonical patterns the 2 closest patterns were merged, this was repeated until only 8 remained (Neal et al., 2016), this produces, for example, a rather generic 1st pattern.

To attempt to account for these sources of uncertainty in subsequent analyses, the patterns in each window are compared to reference patterns from the first window as well as to the set of canonical patterns. Additionally, the pattern generation was repeated for 8 and 30 clusters, and for different numbers of clusters in the range 5 to 10. These uncertainties could potentially be reduced in future by:

- Re-gridding from ERA5 to EMSLP grids when comparing patterns, rather than the other way around, though this would remove some fine structure from the patterns.
- Cluster on the extended ERA5 dataset 1950-2025 (Bell et al., 2021).

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

- Generate a new set of canonical WPs to compare to using the extended ERA5 dataset (Bell et al., 2021), covering 1950-2003 to cover as much of the same period as the original patterns.
- Further explore dimensionality reduction techniques to find clearer cluster structures in the MSLP data, with improved cluster definition and separation.
- Add ancillary meteorological fields when finding clusters such as the daily-mean 2m temperature.
- Explore and fine tune deterministic clustering methods such as k-medoids, DBSCAN, agglomerative, and PCA-Part (Boykin, 2023; Celebi & Kingravi, 2012; Pedregosa et al., 2011) to replace k-means.

5.5. Results

Generating 8 patterns using the first window as the reference window

Figure 20 shows the pattern evolution across time windows when generating 8 patterns and using the first window as the reference window. There is a large increase in distance and a reduction in correlation from the reference patterns, marking a disruptive shift in evolution from the 1986-2001 window onward. The shift is most prominent in the first few windows following the 1986-2001 window but continues until the final 2010-2025 window. The same trend is seen when using the correlation coefficient for pattern assignment instead of the distance (not shown).

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 20: Plots assessing spatial changes in weather patterns over time for a moving 15-year window, within the 1979-2025 period. Using the first window (labelled window 0) as the reference window. Patterns assigned using the Decider distance and LSAP. Pattern evolution heatmap (top), stacked area plot of Decider distances across windows (middle), and correlation coefficients across windows (bottom).

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 21: Assigned pattern distances across time windows for each reference pattern, corresponding to Figure 20. The distance is the area weighted grid point average sum-of-squares difference from the reference patterns in window 0. A smaller distance corresponds to a better fit to the reference pattern features in terms of intensity. Here the patterns matched to reference pattern 3 show the worst fit overall and contribute the most to the overall trend in distance.

The distance stacked area plot and the correlation coefficient heatmap in Figure 20 show the overall trend is predominantly due to patterns assigned to reference window pattern 3. This is clear when looking at trends for individual patterns in Figure 21. The initial rise in distance is also visible for every pattern. In Figure 22, the pressure patterns reveal a shift in reference pattern 3 from a cyclonic westerly with a deep low south of Iceland (effectively canonical pattern 20 of 30, or 2 of 8), to a neutral north-westerly with a low northeast of the UK and high pressure over the Azores. Which could equally be assigned to reference pattern 2 (resembling canonical pattern 3 of 8). This suggests the spatial characteristics of reference pattern 3 have changed across time windows and have become less common since the 1980s but start to return in the final window.

Repeating the pattern generation and assignment process for 8 patterns against the first window produces very similar results (not shown), except for a variation in noise in the distances, which lends credence to the reliability of this pseudo-deterministic method.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 22: The changes across time windows for the 8 weather patterns (cluster centroids), showing the Mean Sea Level Pressure (MSLP) values at 2 hPa intervals. The reference window patterns are shown in the leftmost column, with patterns for a subset of successive time windows (windows 8, 16, 24, and 31) in the following columns left to right. Corresponding to Figure 20.

Generating 8 patterns using the canonical patterns as the reference window

Figure 23 shows WP changes across time windows when generating 8 patterns and using the 8 canonical patterns as the reference window. There is a consistently high distance between the canonical patterns and the assigned patterns throughout. The same trend that is visible in Figure 20 is visible here but to a lesser extent, with an increase in distance and a reduction in correlation from the canonical patterns from the 1986-

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

2001 window onward. Canonical patterns 2 and 4 dominate the overall trend in distance (Figure 24) despite remaining spatially similar across windows with correlation coefficients above 0.8 throughout. While this is partly due to the difference in grid resolution, it could suggest there is a change in intensity over time.

Figure 23: Plots assessing spatial changes in weather patterns for a moving 15-year window, within the 1979-2025 period. Using the 8 canonical Decider patterns as the reference window. Patterns assigned using the Decider distance and LSAP. Pattern evolution heatmap (top), stacked area plot of Decider distances across windows (middle), and correlation coefficients across windows (bottom).

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 24: Assigned pattern distances across time windows for each canonical reference pattern, corresponding to Figure 23. The distance is the area weighted grid point average sum-of-squares difference from the canonical patterns. A smaller distance corresponds to a better fit to the canonical pattern features in terms of intensity. Patterns 2 and 4 show the worst fit in terms of intensity.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 25: The changes across time windows for the 8 canonical weather patterns (cluster centroids), showing the Mean Sea Level Pressure (MSLP) values at 2 hPa intervals. The reference window patterns (the 8 canonical Decider patterns) are shown in the leftmost column, with patterns for a subset of successive time windows (windows 0, 10, 20, and 31) in the following columns, left to right. Corresponding to Figure 23.

In Figure 25 the pressure pattern for WPs assigned to canonical pattern 4 starts to resemble canonical pattern 2 more closely as the distance increases (clearly shown for window 20), which would mark a shift from a south-westerly to a positive NAO pattern. To some extent this agrees with the results when using the first window as the reference; the westerlies and positive NAO patterns are associated with the increase in

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

distance. For canonical pattern 2, the assigned pattern distances are fairly consistent throughout except for a drop near the end, whereas WPs assigned to canonical pattern 4 follow the trend of increased distance for windows starting in the late 1980s seen in Figure 20. WPs assigned to canonical patterns 1 and 5 are the least well-correlated and least spatially similar between windows, but the associated distances are quite low. This is partly expected given the different method used to generate these composite canonical patterns, as discussed in section 3.1.2. Weather Patterns, they are generated by combining the MO30 patterns and not directly from clustering. However, as they capture the overall broad-scale flow type and are few in number they are still useful for exploring spatial changes over time and are a useful point of comparison for the results using 30 patterns.

Generating 30 patterns

When finding 30 patterns, the distances between neighbouring cluster centroids in the same window are smaller and so there is a higher degree of similarity between patterns in any given window. Any variability is attenuated because it is more difficult to find and produce consistent patterns and has a knock-on effect when attempting to compare patterns across windows. Where this pattern generation method is reasonably robust for 8 patterns, it is more complicated using 30 patterns. Any trends in the total distance are more difficult to distinguish.

Figure 26 shows an increase in distance over time from the initial window, peaking in the 1996-2011 window, and then decreasing toward the final window. Figure 29 shows a slight reduction in distance over time from the canonical patterns, but with some variability making this less clear. Together these trends suggest the initial time window starts in a period of elevated distance from the canonical patterns and the WPs have been changing across time windows.

Figure 27, Figure 28, Figure 30, and Figure 31 show there are clear trends among individual patterns, if disregarding the noise and spikes in the data, which are more common when generating 30 patterns than 8 due to the increased variability in the method. The source of the trend in total distance can be linked to specific WPs. For instance, WP 30 is a clear contributor to the total distance and the overall trend in both figures. Pattern 30 shows a step up in Figure 27 and a corresponding step down in Figure 30. Most of the WPs show fairly stable distances and correlations, with small contributions to the overall trend. The WPs with the largest contributions to the distance often correspond to westerly variants with cyclonic deep low-pressure systems, Figure 27 WPs 21, 27, and 30, and Figure 30 canonical WPs 24, 26, and 30. The evolution of a subset of canonical WPs are shown as synoptic charts in Figure 32. These do not correspond to the WPs with the largest reductions in correlation over time. The largest drops in correlation mainly correspond to neutral and anticyclonic WPs, showing clear spatial displacements, for example WPs 1, 4, 5, 6, 9, and 14 in Figure 28, and canonical WPs 1, 3, 5, and 9 in Figure 31.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 26: Stacked area plot of assigned distance metric, assessing spatial changes in weather patterns over time for 30 patterns across a moving 15-year window, within the 1979-2025 period. Using the first window as the reference window. Patterns assigned using the Decider distance and LSAP. The distance is the area weighted grid point average sum-of-squares difference from the window 0 patterns. A smaller distance corresponds to a better fit to the pattern features in terms of intensity.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 27: Assigned pattern distances across time windows for each reference pattern in window 0, corresponding to Figure 26. The distance is the area weighted grid point average sum-of-squares difference from the window 0 patterns. A smaller distance corresponds to a better fit to the pattern features in terms of intensity.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 28: Assigned pattern correlation coefficients across time windows for each reference pattern in window 0, corresponding to Figure 26. A higher correlation coefficient corresponds to a better fit to the position of features in the reference pattern.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 29: Stacked area plot of assigned distance metric, assessing spatial changes in weather patterns over time for 30 patterns across a moving 15-year window, within the 1979-2025 period. Using the 30 canonical Decider patterns as the reference window. Patterns assigned using the Decider distance and LSAP. The distance is the area weighted grid point average sum-of-squares difference from the canonical patterns. A smaller distance corresponds to a better fit to the canonical pattern features in terms of intensity.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 30: Assigned pattern distances across time windows for each canonical reference pattern, corresponding to Figure 29. The distance is the area weighted grid point average sum-of-squares difference from the canonical patterns. A smaller distance corresponds to a better fit to the canonical pattern features in terms of intensity.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 31: Assigned pattern correlation coefficients across time windows for each canonical reference pattern, corresponding to Figure 29. A higher correlation coefficient corresponds to a better fit to the position of features in the canonical pattern.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 32: The changes across time windows for a subset of canonical weather patterns 24-30, showing the synoptic Mean Sea Level Pressure (MSLP) values at 2 hPa intervals. The reference window patterns (the canonical Decider patterns) are shown in the leftmost column, with patterns for a subset of successive time windows (windows 0, 10, 20, and 31) in the following columns, left to right. Corresponding to Figure 29.

5.6. Discussion

The results for both 8 and 30 patterns shows that some of the cluster spatial patterns appear different across time windows since the initial 1979-1994 window. It is currently unclear to what extent these differences are evidence for systematic changes on WP morphology, compared to representing uncertainties in the methodology (e.g. the k-means decision boundary is not stable across different windows), or sampling effects, (e.g. influenced by individual events within a window). For the 8-pattern case, there is an increase in the

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

statistical distance measure from both sets of reference patterns, beginning in the 1986-2001 window, peaking and continuing onward before a reduction in the final 2010-2025 window. Similarly, the 30-pattern assessment shows increasing distances across time from the initial window's patterns, peaking in the 1996-2011 window, followed by a gradual decline. However, when compared to the canonical patterns, the 30-pattern assessment shows a gradual reduction in distance over time, with some variability, from the first to last window.

Across all assessments, the most significant contributors to changes in distance are patterns characterised by deep cyclonic activity, typically westerly variants with intense low-pressure systems. Conversely, reductions in correlation are more closely associated with more frequently occurring neutral or anticyclonic patterns.

For the 8 pattern assessments:

- Relative to the first window, patterns assigned to reference pattern 3 are the primary drivers of increased distance. These patterns intensify and undergo large spatial changes before reverting to a pattern resembling the initial state.
- Relative to the canonical patterns, patterns assigned to canonical patterns 2 and 4 show the greatest divergence. Pattern 2 deepens and shifts westward, while pattern 4 undergoes a marked intensification of both the Icelandic low and the Azores high before reverting to resemble the initial canonical pattern.

For the 30 pattern assessments:

- Relative to the first window, patterns assigned to WPs 21, 27, and 30, each associated with deep low-pressure systems, are the primary drivers of increased distance and exhibit intensification with minimal spatial displacement.
- Relative to the canonical patterns, patterns assigned to WPs 24, 26, and 30, each associated with low-pressure westerlies, appear to drive the overall trend in distance. These patterns show some reductions in low-pressure intensity, with only WP 24 showing notable spatial displacement.

While the results consistently indicate interannual variability and long-term trends across time windows, the direction and magnitude of pattern changes differ depending on the reference window and the number of clusters. This divergence and the exhibited trends could be attributed to several sources of uncertainty and bias, building on those already discussed:

- Structural uncertainty: The lack of clearly defined and persistent structures in the pressure data introduces ambiguity in cluster selection. This is a form of systematic uncertainty, where the model structure (e.g. number of clusters, distance metrics, window duration) influences the outcome.
- Methodological bias: Forcing a fixed number of clusters and enforcing one-to-one pattern assignment across time windows may introduce bias, artificially inflating distance measures due to the rigid constraints.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

- Sensitivity bias: Cyclonic WPs with deep low pressure exhibit steep pressure gradients that make them highly sensitive to small spatial or intensity changes. This can disproportionately increase the distance measure, contributing to apparent non-stationarity.
- Representative and scale mismatch bias: The lower resolution of the canonical patterns can miss and underrepresent fine detail pressure features. This can lead to inflated distance metrics when assigning the higher resolution ERA5 based patterns. The mismatch in spatial scale introduces systematic bias that may exaggerate perceived changes in patterns over time.
- Sampling uncertainty: The 15-year time windows may not fully capture low-frequency variability, leading to sampling bias and potential misinterpretation of features.
- Internal variability: The observed changes may reflect natural climate variability (e.g. NAO, SPV) rather than externally forced trends, complicating non-stationarity attribution.

These initial assessments exploring WP stationarity collectively suggest that some of the generated cluster spatial patterns show non-linear and pattern dependent changes across 15-year time windows within the period 1979-2025. The changes associated with cyclonic low pressure westerly patterns (which are less frequently occurring) and anticyclonic high-pressure patterns (more frequently occurring) appears to be independent, with periods of divergence and realignment depending on the pattern. The split in behaviour between less and more frequently occurring patterns bears some resemblance with the frequency-based analysis in Richardson et al., 2018, where over the last 30 years of the dataset, days featuring WPs 12-30 became more frequent at the expense of days featuring WPs 1-11. Exploring links between the distance metric used here and the annual WP occurrences may provide complementary insights into the origins of any potential non-stationarity.

Due to the complexity of assessing WP stationarity and the large amount of uncertainty in this method, it is currently not possible to determine if the results are genuine signs of long-term spatial non-stationarity, or if they are caused by other factors such as natural atmospheric variability or artefacts of the methodological constraints. While the use of multiple reference windows and numbers of clusters provides a more nuanced understanding of the results, it has introduced complexity when interpreting them. This exploratory work has provided a better understanding of the key challenges and sources of uncertainty in assessing WP stationarity. To better assess and understand non-stationarity with this method in future, it would be beneficial to explore and quantify the sensitivity of the results to different length time windows, assignment metrics, and cluster numbers. Additionally, the influence of large-scale drivers on the exhibited trends across time windows is unclear and merits investigation into any relationships with inter-annual variability and longer-term trends. Despite the uncertainties, there is some evidence that WP stationarity should not be assumed but should be carefully considered where WPs are being used in climate attribution studies.

6. Weather patterns to hazards

This section connects the earlier steps of the COMPASS framework to real-world impacts by examining how specific weather patterns (WPs) translate into hazard relevance. Having established in previous chapters the relationships between large-scale drivers and WPs, we now focus on the next link in the chain: how these WPs are associated with hazardous outcomes such as flooding, storm surges, or heat-related extremes. In doing so, we illustrate the role of WPs as the critical bridge between large-scale climate variability and the occurrence of compound events.

As outlined in Section **Error! Reference source not found.**, the MO30 WPs (Neal et al., 2016) have been linked to a range of weather hazards and impacts, with many of these occurring in the winter months in the UK. Some of this research focuses on a single hazard, for example rainfall which can cause fluvial flooding (Richardson et al., 2020), or multiple hazards separately for example surge or waves which can cause coastal flooding (Neal et al., 2018). From this we can infer some information about the likelihood of co-occurring hazards otherwise referred to as multivariate compound events. However, others have gone further in assessing compound events, exploring the relationship between WPs and co-occurring hazards or impacts.

In this section, we explore and summarise the literature on identifying WPs which are linked to winter hazards and impacts for the UK, including research which focuses on both single hazard and compound events. We also present Table 5 which condenses this information, providing a resource which can be used to quickly identify WPs which have been highlighted in literature as being associated with specific hazards or impacts, including those of a compound nature.

Richardson et al. (2018) showed that conditional distributions of daily, regional UK precipitation given each WP were distinct enough from each other to be suitable for further analysis. This was extended further by Richardson et al. (2020), who researched the link between the WPs and extreme regional precipitation in the UK, as part of their development of the Fluvial Decider forecast guidance tool. Assessing exceedances of the 90th, 95th, 99th and 99.7th percentiles of seasonal precipitation, Richardson et al. (2020) identified the WPs associated with extreme precipitation for each HadUK region. The results shown focus on southeast England, southwest England and southern Wales, and northwest England and northern Wales. WPs 20, 21, 29 and 30 are highlighted as being related to extreme precipitation in these regions. There are differences in the probabilities of threshold exceedance for each region, with extreme rainfall with WP20 being particularly likely in the northwest England and northern Wales region and WP21 providing a particularly high probability of extreme rainfall for the southwest England and southern Wales region. The southeast England region meanwhile is more likely than the other two regions to experience exceedances with WP29 and WP30.

Neal et al. (2018) provide a list of WPs which are relevant to coastal flooding in the UK. They examined the distribution of observed daily maximum skew surges and observed daily maximum wave heights for each WP.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Defining a coastal-risk WP for a particular site as one where at least 1% of event samples (in terms of skew surge or wave heights) exceed the warning threshold (the 99.7th percentile skew surge or wave height climatology at each site), they highlight WPs 13, 14, 20, 21, 23, 24, 26, 28, 29, and 30 for skew surge and WPs 11, 13, 14, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30 for wave height. There is some overlap between the WPs highlighted for different sites, which can be categorised as East, West, or South coast; however, several of the WPs are only noted as high-risk for a handful of the 20 sites. Table 5 summarises the WPs which are highlighted as high-risk for the East, West or South coast.

Combining analysis of daily maximum skew surge with high river flow, Hendry et al. (2019) assess the potential for compound flooding due to co-occurrence of coastal and fluvial drivers. They identify WP 30 as being particularly relevant for compound flooding events on the south-western and western UK coast, with WP 20 also driving events for the central western coast and Scotland. WP 21 is also identified for Scotland. On the eastern coast, Hendry et al. (2019) find that high skew surge and river discharge events tend to occur under different WPs, with WP 11 being identified for surge and WPs 11, 24, and 30 being relevant for river discharge.

In order to characterise compound cold events which could have differing impacts on energy, agriculture, transport, and health in the UK, Mattu et al. (2025) explore the relationship between WPs and events which are either cold-dry or cold-wet. Considering a set of regionally representative cities across the UK (Glasgow, Belfast, Newcastle, London, and Plymouth), Mattu et al. (2025) define cold, dry, and wet events by their regional 15th percentile minimum temperature, 15th percentile precipitation, and 85th percentile precipitation respectively, with cold-dry and cold-wet events being combinations of these thresholds being exceeded. There is a spatial influence on the relationship between WPs and compound cold-wet events; WP 28 is linked to the highest frequency of cold-wet events in London, Newcastle and Plymouth at 20%, 18% and 16% respectively, whereas WPs 21 and 22 are linked to the highest frequency of these events in Belfast and WPs 2 and 12 in Glasgow. Mattu et al. (2025) find that cold-dry events occur under a smaller range of WPs than cold-wet events – for cities in the west of the UK the key patterns are WPs 25 and 27, with the remainder of the set of NAO negative patterns and WPs 12 and 17 also highlighted. Broadly speaking, they suggest that cold-dry events are linked to cyclonic patterns and cold-wet events are linked to anti-cyclonic patterns.

Bloomfield et al. (2024) analyse metrics of loss associated with wind gusts and river flow, to identify WPs that are related to compound wind-flood events in the UK. They calculate the storm severity index (SSI) from reference and flood severity index (FSI) reference and consider three types of compound events: days in which SSI and FSI both exceed 0, SSI and FSI both exceed their historical 95th percentile, and SSI and FSI both exceed their historical 99th percentile. Bloomfield et al. (2024) find that the most common WPs for SSI, FSI, and compound events are WPs 26, 29, and 30 which all exhibit cyclones over the UK.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Focusing on the impacts of adverse weather conditions on power outages in the UK, Souto et al. (2024) identify the WPs and transitions which are likely to cause power system failures due to different hazards. They investigate the top three causes of power system failures in winter: wind and gales, lightning strikes, and snow and ice. National Fault Interruption Reporting Scheme (NaFIRS) data regarding weather hazards responsible for power outages were used to compute the frequency of weather-induced outages by weather phenomenon, WP or WP transition, and season. Souto et al. (2024) found that in winter over 50% of outages induced by wind and gale relate to WPs 26 and 30, over 50% of outages caused by lightning strikes occurred during or the day after WPs 20, 23, 26, and 30, and nearly a third of outages induced by snow and ice occurred a few days after WP 27. When assessing relationships for specific regions of the UK (Northeast of England and Southern Scotland), Souto et al. (2024) find that WPs 19 and 27 are also relevant for power outages induced by snow and ice. They also highlight a set of transitions between WPs (including persistence of certain WPs for more than one day) which are important for weather induced power outages, which include WPs 28 and 29 in addition to various combinations of the previously noted patterns.

Table 5 shows that a subset of the MO30 WPs have been linked to the following hazards affecting the UK in winter: high rainfall events (fluvial flooding), storm surge or high wave events (coastal flooding), compound storm surge and high river discharge events (flooding), compound cold-wet or cold-dry events, compound wind and rain events, and wind and gale, snow or ice, or lightning events (power outages). The WPs highlighted are: 2, 11, 12, 13, 14, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, and 30. Neal et al. (2016) ordered the WPs by their historical frequency, with WP1 occurring the most often and WP30 occurring the least often Richardson et al. (2020) also show that WPs 12-30 occur more often in winter (DJF) than in summer (June-July-August (JJA)). Therefore, it is unsurprising that all but two of the patterns highlighted in Table 5 are numbers greater than or equal to 12, with the majority being in the latter half of the WP numbering.

Of the WPs highlighted, none have been linked to all the hazards, with some (e.g. 2, 11, 12, 13) only linked to one or two of the hazards. However, some WPs (e.g. 21, 28, 29, 30) were highlighted in five or six of the papers. Considering the grouping of 8 sub-patterns, all but groups 6 and 8 (high pressure centred over the UK and Azores high, respectively) have been highlighted. Multiple of these studies note differences between the WPs which are impactful for different regions of the UK, even when assessing the same hazard.

Table 5: Summary of UK winter hazards found in the literature to be related to each of the MO30 WPs.

WP	Sub-type	Rainfall	Surge	Wave	Surge and river flow	Cold-wet	Cold-dry	Wind and rain	Power outages
1	3								
2	4					Glasgow (Mattu et al., 2025)(Mattu et al., 2025)			
3	6								
4	2								
5	5								
6	1								
7	7								
8	2								
9	1								
10	8								
11	1			East coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)	East coast –high river flow (Hendry et al., 2019)(Hendry et al., 2019)				
12	4					Glasgow (Mattu et al., 2025)Mattu et al., 2025)			
13	3		East coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)	East and west coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)					
14	3		East and south coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)	East and west coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)	East coast – surge (Hendry et al., 2019)(Hendry et al., 2019)				
15	4								
16	5								
17	5								
18	6								
19	1			East and west coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)			Glasgow (Mattu et al., 2025)(Mattu et al., 2025)		Snow and ice – Northeast of England. Lightning – Northeast of England (Souto et al., 2024)(Souto et al., 2024)
20	2		East and west coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)	East and west coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)	Central western coast and Scotland – Surge, high river flow, and joint events (Hendry et al.,				Wind and gale – Northeast of England, Southern Scotland. Lightning – GB, Northeast of England (Souto et al., 2024)(Souto et al., 2024)

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

					2019)(Hendry et al., 2019)				
21	4	SWE and NWE (Doug Richardson et al., 2020)(Doug Richardson et al., 2020)	West coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)	East and west coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)	Scotland – Surge, high river flow, and joint events (Hendry et al., 2019)(Hendry et al., 2019)	Belfast (Mattu et al., 2025)(Mattu et al., 2025)			
22	5			East and west coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)		Belfast (Mattu et al., 2025)(Mattu et al., 2025)			
23	2	NWE (Doug Richardson et al., 2020)(Doug Richardson et al., 2020)	East coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)	West coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)					Wind and gale – Northeast of England. Lightning – GB, Northeast of England (Souto et al., 2024)(Souto et al., 2024)
24	3		West coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)	East coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)					
25	1			East coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)			Plymouth (Mattu et al., 2025)(Mattu et al., 2025)		
26	2		East, west, and south coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)	East, west, and south coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)				SSI and FSI (Bloomfield et al., 2024)(Bloomfield et al., 2024)	Wind and gale – GB, Northeast of England, Southern Scotland. Snow and ice – Southern Scotland. Lightning – GB, Northeast of England, Southern Scotland. (Souto et al., 2024)(Souto et al., 2024)
27	1			East coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)			Belfast, Glasgow, London, and Plymouth (Mattu et al., 2025)(Mattu et al., 2025)		Snow and ice – GB, Southern Scotland (Souto et al., 2024)(Souto et al., 2024)
28	1		West coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)	East coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)		London, Newcastle, and Plymouth (Mattu et al., 2025)(Mattu et al., 2025)	Belfast, Glasgow, and Newcastle (noting Newcastle is also highlighted for cold-wet events). (Mattu et al., 2025)(Mattu et al., 2025)		Snow and ice – Northeast of England. Transitions for snow and ice – GB (Souto et al., 2024)(Souto et al., 2024)
29	7	SWE (Doug Richardson et al., 2020)(Doug Richardson et al., 2020)	West and south coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)	East, west, and south coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)				SSI and FSI (Bloomfield et al., 2024)(Bloomfield et al., 2024)	Transitions for snow and ice – GB (Souto et al., 2024)(Souto et al., 2024)

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

								2024)(Bloomfield et al., 2024)	
30	2	SWE (Doug Richardson et al., 2020)(Doug Richardson et al., 2020)	East, west, and south coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)	East, west, and south coast (Neal et al., 2018)(Neal et al., 2018)	South-western and western UK coast – Surge, high river flow, and joint events. East coast – high river flow (Hendry et al., 2019)(Hendry et al., 2019)			SSI and FSI (Bloomfield et al., 2024)(Bloomfield et al., 2024)	Wind and gale – GB, Northeast of England, Southern Scotland. Lightning – UK, Northeast of England (Souto et al., 2024)(Souto et al., 2024)

Table 5 is by no means exhaustive for winter compound events; there are hazards which have not yet (to our knowledge) been linked to the MO30 WPs and there are additional combinations of compound events which have not been explicitly assessed. For example, Hendry et al. (2019) assess WPs linked to compound flooding when two hazards are extreme but also note that they can occur when just one flood source is extreme or when two moderate flooding sources combine to create a flood event. They recommend that these additional categories of events should be recognized in future studies into flood risk.

Furthermore, the studies summarized in Table 5 assess relationships between WPs and hazards or impacts for either the UK as a whole or for broad regions; if applying the framework from Figure 2 we recommend applying specific analysis for the region of interest. However, the methods described in this section should provide a starting point for linking the MO30 to hazards and impacts.

In order to apply the framework presented in this report more broadly, for example to summer hazards in the UK, or to a different region entirely, an equivalent table to Table 5 could be produced. For example, Richardson et al. (2018) analyse both summer and winter UK monthly precipitation climatology in relation to the MO30, Huang et al. (2020) identify WPs associated with excess mortality in the UK in summer and winter, and Whitford et al. (2024) identify the WPs associated with summer sub-daily rainfall extremes in western Europe including the UK.

Beyond the North Atlantic region, a similar methodology to that of Neal et al. (2016) has been applied to create a set of WPs for India Neal et al. (2020), South Africa Ireland et al. (2024), and the Gulf of Mexico Steele et al. (2023).

7. Case study

This chapter demonstrates the COMPASS framework in practice through a case study of the 2013/14 Somerset flooding (Use Case 2a from deliverable D4.1, the UK winter storms of 2013/2014). Building on the earlier analyses of large-scale drivers (Chapter 4), weather pattern stationarity (Chapter 5), and WP–hazard linkages (Chapter 6), we bring these elements together to examine how large-scale drivers influenced the occurrence of hazardous WPs during this extreme winter. The case study illustrates how the framework can move from conceptual steps to a concrete application, providing insight into both the scientific process and the practical value of this approach.”

The selected UK winter storms of 2013/2014 are of note because a series of storms affected the UK over a three-month period. These led to widespread impacts over the UK, mainly in the form of flooding and coastal damage leading to extensive power outages. A combination of sustained heavy rainfall (with successive storms bringing record levels of rainfall onto already saturated ground), high spring tides and strong wind exacerbated the impacts, fuelling conditions for multiple flood types. Use Case 2a focuses on the floods of the Somerset Levels and Moors, which accounted for around 30% of flooded agricultural land nationwide.

Table 5 identifies that WPs 20, 21, 23, 24, 26, 28, 29, and 30 are related to heavy precipitation and storm surge, the combination of hazards relevant for this case study. In particular, Richardson et al. (2020) highlight that around 75% of rainfall in the 3-month period occurred under WPs 30, 29, and 21 (in descending order). This is especially interesting given the temporally compounding nature of this event. In addition, all three WPs were highlighted by Neal et al. (2018) as being linked to storm surge on the west coast. If the frequency of days in 2013/2014 assigned to WPs 21, 29 and 30 was unusually high compared to other winters, and this higher frequency can be related to the large-scale climate drivers preceding or encompassing this period, then this information could be incorporated into a conditional climate change attribution study.

7.1. Methods

To demonstrate step 6 of the proposed framework, we apply Causal Inference theory to assess and better understand the relationship between large-scale drivers and the two WPs linked to the highest rainfall during the case study period, WPs 29 and 30.

Using dataset D3.3, the relationship between each of the large-scale drivers listed in Table 5 and the frequency of WPs 29 and 30 in the corresponding January and February season is explored. The Pearson correlation coefficient is calculated for each combination of large-scale driver and WP frequency. The magnitude of large-scale drivers and the frequency of WPs is highlighted for year of interest for the case study, 2014.

Causal relationships between each of the large-scale drivers and the frequency of WPs 29 and 30 are assessed. An initial causal network is defined using a DAG based on that presented by Sexton et al. (2025), where the

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

drivers of winter North Atlantic circulation are also linked to the frequency of WPs 29 and 30 in the corresponding January-February via a single arrow from the Atlantic Jet to the frequency of WP occurrence. The R packages “dagitty” (Textor et al., 2017) and “ggdag” Barrett (n.d.) are used to check for any missing conditional dependencies between variables using a linear conditional independence test. If any missing links are found, then these are added to the DAG. For each of the direct neighbours of the frequency of WPs in the DAG, the adjustment set is identified. This is the set of additional variables which must be accounted for in order to calculate an unbiased estimate of the causal effect of a variable.

Assuming linear relationships between the variables, a multiple linear regression is used (implemented in R) to estimate the causal effects. The estimated causal network is referred to as a Structural Causal Model (SCM; Pearl et al., 2016) which is a set of linear equations, with one equation for each endogenous node (the variables which have an arrow coming into them) of the DAG. Each endogenous variable can be expressed as a linear sum of its parent nodes multiplied by the relevant causal effect, plus a noise term. The noise terms should be independent of each other and uncorrelated with the exogenous variables (those without an arrow coming into them). If this assumption holds and the causal network also assumes linearity between variables, then the equations of the SCM can be applied sequentially in order to predict the endogenous variables as a function of endogenous variables and noise terms (Sexton et al., 2025). The frequency of the WPs must be standardized (as the large-scale driver values already have been) before the multiple linear regression models are fitted, otherwise the noise term will not have a mean of zero.

The SCM is used to reconstruct the expected frequency of WPs 29 and 30 for each year by substituting the values of the immediate causal drivers. The utility of the causal network to predict the frequency of both WPs is assessed by comparing the predicted frequency of the WPs for each year to the observed frequency. The coefficient of determination (R^2) is calculated for the causal networks, to calculate the proportion of the variation in the frequency of WPs which is explained by our causal network. Focusing on the year of the event (2014) the possibility of the large-scale drivers having a causal effect on the observed frequency of WP29 and 30 is assessed.

7.2. Results

7.2.1. Correlation

First exploring the individual relationships between the large-scale drivers and the frequency of WPs in a season,

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 33 shows scatterplots of the frequency of WP 29 in January-February of each year against each of the large-scale drivers (one per facet), with the Spearman's rank correlation coefficient and p-value for each combination labelled on the plot. The point corresponding to the year of the event (2014) is shown in orange.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 33 shows that 2014 had the 4th most occurrences of WP29 in the observations since 1961. At the alpha=0.05 significant level, only two of the drivers show a significant correlation with the frequency of WP29: DJF AtlJet and JF NAO. DJF AtlJet shows a correlation of 0.41, meaning that as the AtlJet value increases the occurrence of WP 29 also increases. The correlation between WP 29 and JF NAO is -0.48, meaning that lower (more negative) values of the NAO are associated with more frequent occurrences of WP 29. However, the values for both drivers in 2014 (and preceding months of 2013) appear to be around the centre of the distribution. Conversely, considering the drivers which do not have significant correlation with the WP frequency, the values for the AtlDipole, BKSIC, and QBO were particularly high for this year, and the Urals MSLP was one of the smallest in the record. Referring back to the figures in Section 4, WP 29 showed a

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

positive association with DJF AtlJet , OND BKSIC, ASO ENSO, and OND IOD, and a negative association with JF NAO, DJF QBO, DJF SPV, SON UralsMSLP. The direction of association for DJF AtlJet and JF NAO are the same whether considering the frequency of occurrence in a season, or just the coincidence of the WP, but there are differences of the other associations are significant.

Figure 34 shows the equivalent of

Figure 33 but for WP 30 instead of 29, highlighting that only one year since 1961 has had more occurrences of WP30 than 2014. The only large-scale driver showing a significant correlation with frequency of WP30 is JF NAO, with a Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient of 0.42. This positive correlation means that higher (more positive) values of the NAO in JF are associated with more occurrences of WP30 during JF. Figures in Section 4

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

show that WP30 is positively associated with DJF Aleut Low, AtIDiole, IOD, NAO, QBO, SPV and negatively associated with AtlJet. As with WP 29, the direction of association for NAO is the same whether considering the frequency of occurrence in a season, or just the coincidence of the WP. In both cases, this shows the importance of removing the temporal dependence in the data.

Figure 33: Scatterplots showing the frequency of WP29 in January-February of a year against the value of a driver from Table 5 in the same year, with each driver shown by a different plot facet. The Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, R , is shown for each driver, as is the corresponding p -value.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 34: Scatterplots showing the frequency of WP30 in January-February of a year against the value of a driver from Table 5 in the same year, with each driver shown by a different plot facet. The Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, R , is shown for each driver, as is the corresponding p -value.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

7.2.2. Casual inference

To estimate the causal effect of large-scale drivers on the frequency of WPs 29 and 30 during January-February we assume that the most relevant large-scale drivers are those closest to the North Atlantic region (i.e. those which have direct links to NAO in Sexton et al. (2025)’s causal network). Initially, we assume a DAG which links DJF AtlJet to frequency of WP 29 or 30 during JF. This has 57 implied conditional independencies. Using the “dagitty” package, we test at the alpha = 0.05 level for any additional dependencies, finding that there should be an additional one between JF NAO and the frequency of WP 29 or 30. There is also a dependency suggested from SPV to ENSO, however this is disregarded as it would create a feedback loop in the DAG. As NAO is considered an inherent part of North Atlantic circulation, rather than a driver of North Atlantic circulation, it is unclear whether it should be included as a causal effect of the WPs. Therefore, we repeat the process with and without including the NAO.

Figure 35 shows the DAG representing a causal network which links large-scale drivers to frequency of WPs 29 or 30 via the DJF Atlantic Jet. Using the “dagitty” package in R, we identify the set of large-scale drivers which must be adjusted in order to estimate an unbiased causal effect of AtlJet on the frequency of WP29/30. While Pearl et al. (2016) describe several possible adjustment methods, we follow Sexton et al. (2025) by including additional variables (those from the adjustment set) as covariates in a multiple linear regression between the “predictor” and “target” variable.

Figure 35: DAG showing a causal network between large-scale drivers and the frequency of WP29 or 30, with a direct link from DJF Ajet. Causal strengths are provided in the text below, for only the direct causal effects between a large-scale driver and the frequency of WP29 or 30.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 36: DAG showing the casual network from Figure 35 (i.e. between large-scale drivers and the frequency of WP29 or 30, with a direct link from DJF Ajet , but with the addition of colour to show which variables should be adjusted (orange) or unadjusted (blue) when estimating the direct causal effect of DJF Ajet on the frequency WP29 or 30. Here, adjustment is done by the addition of the variables highlighted in orange in the multiple linear regression used to estimate the causal effect.

Standardising the values for frequency of WP29 and 30 (subtracting the mean and dividing by the sample standard deviation), we estimate the causal effect of DJF AtlJet by fitting a multiple linear regression with the additional terms suggested by Figure 35. However, because the frequency of WP29 and 30 is a count value, which would follow a Poisson distribution, it does not satisfy the assumption of Normally-distributed variables for linear regression. The limitations of this approach are discussed further in Section 8. The diagnostic plots for this multiple linear regression are shown by Figure 62 and Figure 65 in Annex B. Using the regression coefficient for AtlJet, we can construct the following equations, where X represents a variable and U represents a normally distributed noise term with mean 0 and standard deviation σ :

$$X_{Freq29} = 0.96 X_{AtlJet} + U_{Freq29}$$

$$X_{Freq30} = 0.21 X_{AtlJet} + U_{Freq30}$$

We also estimate an alternative network incorporating the NAO. In the case of WP 29, we find that an additional dependency from UralsMSLP is required. Figure 37 shows the updated causal network for WP 29 and Figure 38 shows the updated causal network for WP 30. Again, we identify the drivers which must be controlled for in order to estimate an unbiased causal effect on WP29 and 30. The adjusted variables for Atlantic Jet remain the same as before. The variables which must be adjusted for NAO and Urals (in the case of WP29) are shown in Figure 39 and Figure 40 respectively.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 37: DAG showing a causal network between large-scale drivers and the frequency of WP29 with direct links from DJF Ajet, JF NAO and Urals MSLP. This differs from Figure 35 due to the inclusion of direct links from JF NAO and Urals MSLP, and that it only applies to WP29. Causal strengths are provided in the text below, for only the direct causal effects between a large-scale driver and the frequency of WP29.

Figure 38: DAG showing a causal network between large-scale drivers and the frequency of WP30 with direct links from Ajet and JF NAO. This differs from Figure 35 due to the inclusion of direct links from JF NAO, and that it only applies to WP30. Causal strengths are provided in the text below, for only the direct causal effects between a large-scale driver and the frequency of WP 30.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 39: DAG showing the casual network from Figure 37 (i.e. between large-scale drivers and the frequency of WP 29, with a direct link from DJF Ajet, JF NAO and SON UralsMSLP, but with the addition of colour to show which variables should be adjusted (orange) or unadjusted (blue) when estimating the direct causal effect of JF NAO on the frequency of WP29. The same adjustment set applies when estimating the direct effect of JF NAO on the frequency of WP30, when the only other direct effect is DJF Ajet. Here, adjustment is done by the addition of the variables highlighted in orange in the multiple linear regression used to estimate the causal effect.

Figure 40: DAG showing the casual network from Figure 37 (i.e. between large-scale drivers and the frequency of WP 29, with a direct link from DJF Ajet, JF NAO and SON UralsMSLP, but with the addition of colour to show which variables should be adjusted (orange) or unadjusted (blue) when estimating the direct causal effect of SON UralsMSLP on the frequency of WP29. Here, adjustment is done by the addition of the variables highlighted in orange in the multiple linear regression used to estimate the causal effect.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Blocking relevant paths, we estimate the causal effect of DJF AtlJet and JF NAO (and Urals MSLP in the case of WP 29). The diagnostic plots for each multiple linear regression are shown by Figure 64, Figure 65, and Figure 66 in Annex B. Using the regression coefficient from each multiple linear regression, we construct the following equations

$$X_{Freq29} = 0.96 X_{AtlJet} - 0.73 X_{NAO} + 0.21 X_{UralsMSLP} + U_{Freq29}$$

$$X_{Freq30} = 0.21 X_{AtlJet} + 0.50 X_{NAO} + U_{Freq30}$$

Next, we use the causal effects to estimate the frequency of WP 29 and 30 given the driver values, for the version of the networks with and without the NAO. Figure 41 shows a scatterplot of the predicted frequency of WP 29 using AtlJet against the observed frequency and a time series of the predicted and observed frequency of WP 29 for each year. Figure 42 shows the equivalent but using AtlJet, NAO and UralsMSLP to predict the frequency. The standard deviation of the residuals – the difference between the predicted and observed values – (i.e. the value of the noise term) when predicting the frequency of WP 29 using AtlJet alone is 0.97, and 0.91 with the addition of NAO and UralsMSLP. When predicting the frequency of WP 30, the standard deviation of the residuals is 1.01 when using AtlJet only, and decreases to 0.91 when NAO is also included.

Figure 41 indicates that the causal effect of the AtlJet only explains 6.4% of the variability in the frequency of WP29, whereas including the causal effect of NAO and UralsMSLP explains 24% of the variability. For 2014 this means that the expected (standardized) frequency of WP 29 given the AtlJet, NAO and UralsMSLP values is much lower than the observed frequency. Some unphysical, negative frequencies are predicted as a result of applying ordinary linear regression to count (frequency) data. The scatterplot also shows the difference in distribution between the observed and predicted frequencies, with the observed frequency showing a longer tail more consistent with a Poisson distribution and the predicted frequency appearing more in line with a Normal distribution (as expected with predictions from a linear regression model). This supports the use of a Poisson model in any future work (discussed further in Section 8).

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 41: Plots showing the performance of the predicted standardised frequency of WP29 using causal effect of Atlantic Jet only, with a scatterplot of the predicted frequency against the observed frequency with the $y=x$ line in blue (left) and time series plot of the observed (black line) and predicted frequency (orange line) (right).

Figure 42: Plots showing the performance of the predicted standardised frequency of WP29 using causal effect of Atlantic Jet, NAO and Urals MSLP, with a scatterplot of the predicted frequency against the observed frequency with the $y=x$ line in blue (left) and time series plot of the observed (black line) and predicted frequency (orange line) (right).

The equivalent plots to Figure 41 and Figure 42 but predicting the frequency of WP30 are shown in Figure 43 (AtlJet only) and Figure 44 (AtlJet and NAO). Whereas Figure 43 shows that the causal effect of the AtlJet explains an almost negligible proportion of the variability in the frequency of WP30, Figure 44 shows that also including the causal effect of NAO explains 19% of the variability. This is still a relatively small proportion, and the predicted frequency for 2013/2014 is much lower than the observed frequency. This underestimation could be due to the frequency data following a Poisson distribution, with ordinary linear regression not capturing the strength of this relationship. As with WP 29, some unphysical, negative frequencies are predicted.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 43: Plots showing the performance of the predicted standardised frequency of WP30 using causal effect of Atlantic Jet only, with a scatterplot of the predicted frequency against the observed frequency with the $y=x$ line in blue (left) and time series plot of the observed (black line) and predicted frequency (orange line) (right).

Figure 44: Plots showing the performance of predicted standardised frequency of WP30 using causal effect of Atlantic Jet and NAO, with a scatterplot of the predicted frequency against the observed frequency with the $y=x$ line in blue (left) and time series plot of the observed (black line) and predicted frequency (orange line) (right).

For both WPs 29 and 30, we conclude that whilst the NAO has a statistically significant causal effect on the frequency, there is still a large amount of variability in frequency of occurrence which is not explained. The other large-scale drivers which have a significant causal effect only capture a negligible amount of variability. It is possible that the relationship between the drivers we have analysed is non-linear and so cannot be captured by the linear assumptions of our SCM, or alternatively that a different transformation of the weather pattern frequency (i.e. a log transformation rather than standardisation) would be more appropriate. These possibilities are backed up by the non-linear shape of the scatter in many facets of

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 33 and Figure 34, and the poor diagnostic plots shown in Annex B. There may also be key drivers missing from the original causal network, or as Sexton et al. (2025) allude to, there may be a component of variability in winter North Atlantic circulation which truly is unpredictable noise.

Overall, the Somerset case study demonstrates how large-scale drivers could be traced through their influence on weather patterns to explain the likelihood of a specific compound flooding event. Taking insights from causal inference, the framework provides a structured way to understand the drivers behind impactful extremes. This case study highlights the potential for applying the COMPASS framework to other regions and event types, setting the stage for the broader discussion in Chapter 8 on lessons learned, limitations, and priorities for future research.

8. Discussion

Key findings

This report has presented a framework for understanding the relationships between large-scale drivers and weather types in the context of compound extremes. Using the example of winter North Atlantic circulation and weather types relevant to Use Case 2a from deliverable D4.1, we have demonstrated the extension of a causal network of large-scale drivers and methods for assessing stationarity of WPs.

This work has found that while there are significant global associations between a set of large-scale drivers of winter North Atlantic circulation and WPs for the UK, each driver only shows significant local associations with a subset of the 30 WPs. When considering the frequency of WPs selected specifically for their influence on wet and stormy conditions in the South West of England, the only drivers found to have significant correlations are the JF NAO and DJF AtlJet. However, the NAO is not technically classed as a large-scale driver for North Atlantic circulation. Strong relationships have been found by previous studies between a range of winter hazards including compound events in the UK, however these are generally not assessed for causality. In particular, WPs 29 and 30 from Neal et al. (2016) were identified as being relevant for the 2013/2014 winter storms in the UK. A causal network was extended from the large-scale drivers to the selected WPs, showing the potential for Causal Inference to be used to link large-scale drivers to compound events through WPs. Although this causal network, for the specific case study, was not able to capture most of the variability in the frequency of the key WPs, with further development or a different case study the framework shows potential to identify, assess and understand the links between large-scale drivers and compound events.

Challenges

While there is a lot of uncertainty in the results of the WP stationarity assessments across time windows, the work has provided a clearer understanding of the challenges and uncertainties in performing WP stationarity assessments and underscores the importance of accounting for WP non-stationarity when applying WPs in attribution studies and compound event analysis.

The case study used to demonstrate the framework is limited by the result that the large-scale drivers assessed only explain a small proportion of the variability in the frequency of WPs 29 and 30. This means that while it was identified that the NAO and to a lesser extent, the AtlJet (and UralsMSLP for WP 29), have a statistically significant causal effect on the frequency of the WPs, this effect is too small to be able to make meaningful statements about the increased frequency of these WPs during the winter of 2013/2014 due to the large-scale drivers. If the NAO considered to be a representation of the state of North Atlantic circulation rather than one of its drivers, then the proportion of variability explained by large-scale drivers is even smaller. Consequently, it was not possible to proceed to the next stage of the framework, where the large-scale drivers

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

could be linked to increased likelihood of the hazards (i.e. heavy precipitation over a season and storm surge) using causal links with WPs.

Whilst the causal network from Sexton et al. (2025) captures causal effects between large-scale drivers and JF NAO, there appear to be factors in the high occurrence of WPs 29 and 30 in 2014 which are not reflected in the current causal network. This may be down to missing large-scale drivers from winter North Atlantic circulation in general, missing drivers for the specific conditions which were relevant in 2014 in particular, or the invalidity of the linear assumptions. The case study has demonstrated the difficulty in capturing the complexity of teleconnections and large-scale drivers within specific indices (i.e. averaging a single meteorological variable over a fixed space and time).

Considering the scalability of the framework, it is worth noting that defining a set of WPs is a complex task. If looking to understand weather types, large scale drivers and compound events for an area without pre-defined weather types then this may not be practical. To make this framework more widely applicable, further research and development would be needed to provide an automated or semi-automated method to define WPs for a given region. This could build upon the methods presented in Section 5.

Next steps

The methods used to explore WP stationarity could be developed further to improve the robustness and flexibility of the clustering and assignment methods, and assess sensitivity to different time window lengths, cluster numbers, grid resolutions, assignment metrics, and clustering and dimensionality reduction techniques. Analysis of annual WP occurrences and links between frequency and trends in the distance from this method could be explored to gain further insights into the source of changes in distance across time windows. The technique could be applied to more WPs and domains, and to climate projections to help separate any forced trends from natural variability, and begin to explore how WPs might change spatially into the future.

There are several ways by which the case study demonstration could be continued in search of a more definitive causal link between large-scale drivers and the frequency of WPs 29 and 30. In its simplest form, this analysis could continue by estimating non-linear relationships between the variables (both between different combinations of large-scale drivers, and between the drivers and the frequency of WPs). For example, this could be implemented using a Generalised Linear Model with Poisson-distributed residuals (to account for the fact that the frequency of WPs is a count, typically represented by a Poisson distribution, rather than the assumed Normal distribution required for a linear regression). Alternatively, a Generalised Additive Model could be used to estimate non-linear relationships and interactions between variables whilst retaining explainability. A benefit of Causal Inference theory is that once the DAG has been defined, a range of statistical methods can be used to estimate the causal effect between variables. However, the properties of the SCM

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

around sequentially applying linear combinations of the variables and causal effects will no longer hold, increasing the complexity of the process.

A stronger causal link between large-scale drivers and the frequency of WPs 29 and 30 might also be found by exploring additional large-scale drivers outside of those suggested by Sexton et al. (2025). It may be that a more specialized causal network, with drivers selected specifically for their propensity to cause specific WPs to occur in the North Atlantic region during winter, could perform better than a causal network initially created for winter North Atlantic circulation as a whole. For example, Huntingford et al. (2014) highlighted that in addition to the positive NAO at the time, other drivers may have included heavy rainfall in the tropical Pacific strengthening the Atlantic jet stream; westerly wind adjustment in the upper troposphere in the East Pacific allowing for additional disturbances to enter the Atlantic Jet stream's origin; and teleconnection from the QBO in a strong westerly phase over the tropics increasing the pressure gradient in the Atlantic. This suggests that further exploring links between the Atlantic jet stream, conditions in the East Pacific, the QBO, and the pressure gradient in the Atlantic could improve the causal network. Although some of these drivers are already included in the winter North Atlantic causal network, it may be that different combinations of months are more relevant for the specific conditions from this case study. This also raises broader considerations for the framework around how generalizable each stage should be; should the same network of large-scale drivers be used for all WPs or all compound events in a particular region?

One of the key decisions in the analysis of Sections 4 and 7 is to use the detrended large-scale drivers, following Sexton et al. (2025), and in particular to apply the detrending after standardisation rather than before. For variables with a strong trend, this will result in a standard deviation of below 1, which may lead to the causal strengths for these variables being artificially high. The effect of this detrending on the results presented in this report may be sensitive to this decision, particularly those regarding BKSIC. Although BKSIC was not thought to be a direct driver of the winter WPs, more research is required to understand the sensitivity of the causal effects to detrending. In future work, standardisation should instead be applied after any detrending. The implications of detrending large-scale drivers when drawing inferences for conditional climate attribution studies should also be considered.

The use of Causal Inference in this framework could be expanded to assess the causal relationship between WPs and compound events, rather than simply assessing correlations as the studies referenced in Section 6 do. This could enable a causal network which stretches the whole way from large-scale drivers and teleconnections to WPs to the hazards responsible for compound event and would increase the robustness of the methodology. Alternative methods for selecting the WPs to focus on could also be explored – returning to the theme of generalizability of the framework, grouping the WPs into clusters based on the similarities of the hazards they are associated with would provide a smaller set of patterns to separately link to the large-scale

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

drivers. Whilst Neal et al. (2016) also provide a set of 8 WPs which the 30 patterns can be collapsed into, these are defined based on similarity of the circulation patterns rather than similarity of the observable weather conditions that they are responsible for.

The dataset D3.3 presents opportunities for further research outside of the case study presented in this report. Theoretically, any weather hazard in the area covered by the MO30 WPs could be assessed using the framework provided, with links between any of the 30 WPs and the large-scale drivers from Table 5 being available for analysis. It is possible that some of these demonstrate inherently stronger causal relationships than those assessed here. The framework of this report is also applicable to other seasons and regions. For example, if a similar causal network was constructed for North Atlantic circulation at a different time of year (e.g. summer) then this could be linked to the MO30 WPs in the same way that D3.3 was created, in order to link large-scale drivers to compound events such as the heatwave-drought of 2022 in the UK. This report has described methods from the literature which can be used to identify large-scale drivers and objectively characterise weather types for a region. The methods used to link large-scale drivers to weather types could be applied to any set of drivers, and weather types. For example, the WPs defined for South Africa Ireland et al. (2024) or India Neal et al. (2020) could be used.

9. Conclusion

This report has presented the COMPASS framework which can be used to identify, assess, and understand large-scale drivers and weather types which give rise to compound extremes. Taking insights from causal inference, a step-by-step approach is proposed which identifies the potential large-scale drivers and weather types which are relevant for a particular compound event, assesses the relationships between the drivers, weather types and compound events, and finally evaluates causal effects in order to generate causal understanding of these relationships. This framework is demonstrated using the example of winter North Atlantic circulation, and specifically a case study of the UK winter storms of 2013/2014.

Having introduced the motivation for better understanding the links between weather types, large-scale drivers and compound events in the context of compound event attribution, a schematic diagram is used to present the steps of the framework. A description of the types of methods that each step could encompass is also provided, with summaries of relevant literature provided where appropriate.

A dataset linking large-scale drivers of winter North Atlantic circulation and WPs relevant for the UK has been produced. This data is made publicly available as part of deliverable D2.3. The contributing data used to produce this dataset is described in detail, as well as the methods used for pre-processing and linking the two sets of data. A description of the files available from deliverable D2.3 is also provided.

The dataset is then analysed, first to directly explore the associations between the large-scale drivers and the WPs. The global and local association between seasonally aggregated large-scale drivers and the WPs in the corresponding January-February is assessed with significance testing and (in the case of the local association) the direction of the associations is also shown. The relationships between the frequency of each WP in a January-February period and the large-scale drivers are also explored graphically.

To begin to test the assumption of WP stationarity, k-means clustering is used to generate patterns for multiple time windows to explore how individual WPs diverge and change spatially across time windows when assigned to the canonical WPs using the Decider distance measure.

In order to demonstrate how WPs can be linked to hazards as part of the framework, a review of studies linking the WPs to winter weather conditions in the UK is conducted. This outlines methods and results of studies assessing the relationships between WPs and a range of hazards and impacts, both single-hazard and compound events, from flooding to power outages. The results of this review are summarized in a table, which highlights the hazards and impacts which have been linked in the literature to each of the 30 WPs from Neal et al. (2016). Potential avenues for applying this step of the framework to other seasons or regions are also outlined.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

A case study, the UK winter storms of 2013/2014, is used to demonstrate how large-scale drivers can be linked to specific WPs which are relevant for a particular type of compound event. Two WPs are identified as being particularly relevant for the temporal extent of the wet and stormy conditions that winter. The relationship between each of the large-scale drivers in the dataset and the key WPs is assessed, particularly focusing on the number of times that those WPs occurred in January and February of 2014 compared to in order years. The significance of the correlation between the large scale drivers and frequency of the key WPs' occurrence is tested. Causal inference is used to estimate the causal effect of specific large-scale drivers on the frequency of key weather patterns in a given year, building upon the causal network of Sexton et al. (2025). The estimated causal network is used to predict the expected frequency of key WPs in January and February of each year including 2014, given the value of certain large-scale drivers. The performance of the causal network is also evaluated graphically and using the coefficient of determination (R^2).

This work has found that there are statistically significant associations between some large-scale drivers of winter North Atlantic circulation and WPs for the UK, with DJF AtlJet showing significant correlation with the frequency of WP 29 in JF. Whilst the performance of the large-scale drivers in predicting the frequency of WP 29 and 30 in JF through an initial causal network is poor, a number of areas for further research and improvements have been identified. The work exploring WP stationarity suggests, albeit with large uncertainty, that the cluster spatial patterns show changes in spatial characteristics across time windows. Whilst further work is required to reduce the large uncertainties in these results, they demonstrate the importance of accounting for non-stationarity and long-term influence when applying the WPs in studies.

A number of recommendations have been identified through this work and discussed in Section 8. There are several ways in which the framework presented here could be applied to different regions or seasons, or specific case studies of interest. In addition, there is potential for further development of the causal network developed for the case study here.

The next step, along with following these recommendations, will be to explore how the information about large-scale drivers elicited through the framework could be used to inform attribution studies.

10. References

- Aleksandrova, N., Vertegaal, D., Couasnon, A., Perks, R., Cotterill, D., Vogel, M., Jack, C., Paprotny, D., Terefenko, P., & Ślodziowski, J. (2024). Guidelines for compound extremes modelling in current and future climates. In *Horizon Europe Project COMPASS. Deliverable D1.1*.
- Amid, E., & Warmuth, M. K. (2022). *TriMap: Large-scale Dimensionality Reduction Using Triplets*. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1910.00204>
- Ansell, T. J., Jones, P. D., Allan, R. J., Lister, D., Parker, D. E., Brunet, M., Moberg, A., Jacobeit, J., Brohan, P., Rayner, N. A., Aguilar, E., Alexandersson, H., Barriendos, M., Brandsma, T., Cox, N. J., Della-Marta, P. M., Drebs, A., Founda, D., Gerstengarbe, F., ... Xoplaki, E. (2006). Daily Mean Sea Level Pressure Reconstructions for the European–North Atlantic Region for the Period 1850–2003. *Journal of Climate*, *19*(12), 2717–2742. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI3775.1>
- Barrett, M. (n.d.). *ggdag: Analyze and Create Elegant Directed Acyclic Graphs. R package version 0.2.13.9000*. Retrieved July 27, 2025, from <https://github.com/r-causal/ggdag>
- Bell, B., Hersbach, H., Simmons, A., Berrisford, P., Dahlgren, P., Horányi, A., Muñoz-Sabater, J., Nicolas, J., Radu, R., Schepers, D., Soci, C., Villaume, S., Bidlot, J.-R., Haimberger, L., Woollen, J., Buontempo, C., & Thépaut, J.-N. (2021). The ERA5 global reanalysis: Preliminary extension to 1950. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, *147*(741), 4186–4227. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.4174>
- Bloomfield, H. C., Bates, P., Shaffrey, L. C., Hillier, J., Champion, A., Cotterill, D., Pope, J. O., & Kumar, D. (2024). Synoptic conditions conducive for compound wind-flood events in Great Britain in present and future climates. *Environmental Research Letters*, *19*(2), 024019. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ad1cb7>
- Boykin, K. A. (2023). *Extracting likely scenarios from ensemble forecasts in real-time*. <https://centaur.reading.ac.uk/111270/>
- Buschow, S., Friederichs, P., & Hense, A. (2024). *Reconciling risk-based and storyline attribution with Bayes theorem*.
- Celebi, M. E., & Kingravi, H. A. (2012). Deterministic Initialization of the K-Means Algorithm Using Hierarchical Clustering. *International Journal of Pattern Recognition and Artificial Intelligence*, *26*(07), 1250018. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218001412500188>
- Cotterill, D. F., Pope, J. O., & Stott, P. A. (2023). Future extension of the UK summer and its impact on autumn precipitation. *Climate Dynamics*, *60*(5–6), 1801–1814. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-022-06403-0>
- Crouse, D. F. (2016). On implementing 2D rectangular assignment algorithms. *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, *52*(4), 1679–1696. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAES.2016.140952>
- Garry, F., & Palmer, D. (2025). *Arctic Weather Patterns and Sea Ice in a Changing Climate*.
- Hendry, A., Haigh, I. D., Nicholls, R. J., Winter, H., Neal, R., Wahl, T., Joly-Laugel, A., & Darby, S. E. (2019). Assessing the characteristics and drivers of compound flooding events around the UK coast. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, *23*(7), 3117–3139. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-23-3117-2019>
- Hersbach, H., Bell, B., Berrisford, P., Hirahara, S., Horányi, A., Muñoz-Sabater, J., Nicolas, J., Peubey, C., Radu, R., Schepers, D., Simmons, A., Soci, C., Abdalla, S., Abellan, X., Balsamo, G., Bechtold, P., Biavati, G., Bidlot, J., Bonavita, M., ... Thépaut, J. (2020). The ERA5 global reanalysis. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, *146*(730), 1999–2049. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3803>

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

- Huang, W. T. K., Charlton-Perez, A., Lee, R. W., Neal, R., Sarran, C., & Sun, T. (2020). Weather regimes and patterns associated with temperature-related excess mortality in the UK: a pathway to sub-seasonal risk forecasting. *Environmental Research Letters*, *15*(12), 124052. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abcbb>
- Huntingford, C., Marsh, T., Scaife, A. A., Kendon, E. J., Hannaford, J., Kay, A. L., Lockwood, M., Prudhomme, C., Reynard, N. S., Parry, S., Lowe, J. A., Screen, J. A., Ward, H. C., Roberts, M., Stott, P. A., Bell, V. A., Bailey, M., Jenkins, A., Legg, T., ... Allen, M. R. (2014). Potential influences on the United Kingdom's floods of winter 2013/14. *Nature Climate Change*, *4*(9), 769–777. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2314>
- Ireland, L. G., Robbins, J., Neal, R., Barciela, R., & Gilbert, R. (2024). Generating weather pattern definitions over <sc>South Africa</sc> suitable for future use in impact-orientated medium-range forecasting. *International Journal of Climatology*, *44*(5), 1513–1529. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.8396>
- Kretschmer, M., Adams, S. V., Arribas, A., Prudden, R., Robinson, N., Saggiaro, E., & Shepherd, T. G. (2021). Quantifying Causal Pathways of Teleconnections. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, *102*(12), E2247–E2263. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-20-0117.1>
- Kretschmer, M., Coumou, D., Donges, J. F., & Runge, J. (2016). Using Causal Effect Networks to Analyze Different Arctic Drivers of Midlatitude Winter Circulation. *Journal of Climate*, *29*(11), 4069–4081. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-15-0654.1>
- Lebart, L., Morineau, A., & Warwick, K. M. (1984). *Multivariate Descriptive Statistical Analysis*. Wiley.
- Maher, P., & Sherwood, S. C. (2014). Disentangling the Multiple Sources of Large-Scale Variability in Australian Wintertime Precipitation. *Journal of Climate*, *27*(17), 6377–6392. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-13-00659.1>
- Manning, C., Kendon, E. J., Fowler, H. J., Catto, J. L., Chan, S. C., & Sansom, P. G. (2024). Compound wind and rainfall extremes: Drivers and future changes over the UK and Ireland. *Weather and Climate Extremes*, *44*, 100673. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wace.2024.100673>
- Mattu, K. L., White, C. J., Bloomfield, H., & Robbins, J. (2025). Characterising Cold-Dry and Cold-Wet Compound Events in the United Kingdom. *International Journal of Climatology*, *45*(9). <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.8859>
- McInnes, L., Healy, J., & Melville, J. (2020). *UMAP: Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection for Dimension Reduction*. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1802.03426>
- Neal, R., Dankers, R., Saulter, A., Lane, A., Millard, J., Robbins, G., & Price, D. (2018). Use of probabilistic medium- to long-range weather-pattern forecasts for identifying periods with an increased likelihood of coastal flooding around the UK. *Meteorological Applications*, *25*(4), 534–547. <https://doi.org/10.1002/met.1719>
- Neal, R., Fereday, D., Crocker, R., & Comer, R. E. (2016). A flexible approach to defining weather patterns and their application in weather forecasting over Europe. *Meteorological Applications*, *23*(3), 389–400. <https://doi.org/10.1002/met.1563>
- Neal, R., Robbins, J., Dankers, R., Mitra, A., Jayakumar, A., Rajagopal, E. N., & Adamson, G. (2020). Deriving optimal weather pattern definitions for the representation of precipitation variability over India. *International Journal of Climatology*, *40*(1), 342–360. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.6215>
- Noyelle, R., Faranda, D., Robin, Y., Vrac, M., & Yiou, P. (2025). Attributing the occurrence and intensity of extreme events with the flow analogue method. *Weather and Climate Dynamics*, *6*(3), 817–839. <https://doi.org/10.5194/wcd-6-817-2025>

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

- Pearl, J., Glymour, M., & Jewell, N. P. (2016). *Causal Inference in Statistics: A Primer* (Vol. 75). John Wiley & Sons Ltd.
- Pearson, K. (1901). On lines and planes of closest fit to systems of points in space. *The London, Edinburgh, and Dublin Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science*, 2(11), 559–572. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786440109462720>
- Pedregosa, F., Varoquaux, G., Gramfort, A., Michel, V., Thirion, B., Grisel, O., Blondel, M., Prettenhofer, P., Weiss, R., Dubourg, V., Vanderplas, J., Passos, A., Cournapeau, D., Brucher, M., Perrot, M., & Duchesnay, É. (2011). Scikit-learn: Machine Learning in Python. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 12(85), 2825–2830. <http://jmlr.org/papers/v12/pedregosa11a.html>
- Perks, R. J., Bernie, D., Lowe, J., & Neal, R. (2023). The influence of future weather pattern changes and projected sea-level rise on coastal flood impacts around the UK. *Climatic Change*, 176(3), 25. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-023-03496-2>
- Philipp, A., Della-Marta, P. M., Jacobeit, J., Fereday, D. R., Jones, P. D., Moberg, A., & Wanner, H. (2007). Long-Term Variability of Daily North Atlantic–European Pressure Patterns since 1850 Classified by Simulated Annealing Clustering. *Journal of Climate*, 20(16), 4065–4095. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI4175.1>
- Pope, J. O., Brown, K., Fung, F., Hanlon, H. M., Neal, R., Palin, E. J., & Reid, A. (2022). Investigation of future climate change over the British Isles using weather patterns. *Climate Dynamics*, 58(9), 2405–2419. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-021-06031-0>
- Richardson, D., Fowler, H. J., Kilsby, C. G., & Neal, R. (2018). A new precipitation and drought climatology based on weather patterns. *International Journal of Climatology*, 38(2), 630–648. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.5199>
- Richardson, D., Neal, R., Dankers, R., Mylne, K., Cowling, R., Clements, H., & Millard, J. (2020). Linking weather patterns to regional extreme precipitation for highlighting potential flood events in medium- to long-range forecasts. *Meteorological Applications*, 27(4). <https://doi.org/10.1002/met.1931>
- Robette, N. (2024). *Descriptio: Descriptive Analysis of Association between Variables in R, Version 1.4*. <https://nicolas-robette.github.io/descriptio/>
- Runge, J., Bathiany, S., Bollt, E., Camps-Valls, G., Coumou, D., Deyle, E., Glymour, C., Kretschmer, M., Mahecha, M. D., Muñoz-Marí, J., van Nes, E. H., Peters, J., Quax, R., Reichstein, M., Scheffer, M., Schölkopf, B., Spirtes, P., Sugihara, G., Sun, J., ... Zscheischler, J. (2019). Inferring causation from time series in Earth system sciences. *Nature Communications*, 10(1), 2553. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-10105-3>
- Sexton, D. M. H. (2024). Data for late winter NAO connections. In *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10908700>
- Sexton, D. M. H., Yamazaki, K., Rostron, J. W., Dunstone, N. J., Fereday, D. R., Hardiman, S. C., Ineson, S., & Knight, J. R. (2025). Effect of resolution on simulated teleconnections to winter North Atlantic circulation inferred from a causal network derived from expert elicitation. *Climate Dynamics*, 63(1), 32. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-024-07497-4>
- Souto, L., Neal, R., Pope, J. O., Gonzalez, P. L. M., Wilkinson, J., & Taylor, P. C. (2024). Identification of weather patterns and transitions likely to cause power outages in the United Kingdom. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 5(1), 49. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-024-01217-w>
- Steele, E., Jaramillo, S., Neal, R., Storie, J., & Zhang, X. (2023, April 24). Prediction of Loop Current and Eddy Regimes in the Gulf of Mexico. *Offshore Technology Conference*. <https://doi.org/10.4043/32615-MS>

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

- Steele, E., Neal, R., Dankers, R., Fournier, N., Mylne, K., Newell, P., Saulter, A., Skea, A., & Upton, J. (2018, April 30). Using Weather Pattern Typology to Identify Calm Weather Windows for Local Marine Operations. *Offshore Technology Conference*. <https://doi.org/10.4043/28784-MS>
- Textor, J., van der Zander, B., Gilthorpe, M. S., Liškiewicz, M., & Ellison, G. T. H. (2017). Robust causal inference using directed acyclic graphs: the R package 'dagitty.' *International Journal of Epidemiology*, dyw341. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyw341>
- van der Maaten, L., & Hinton, G. (2008). Visualizing Data using t-SNE. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 9(86), 2579–2605. <http://jmlr.org/papers/v9/vandermaaten08a.html>
- Virtanen, P., Gommers, R., Oliphant, T. E., Haberland, M., Reddy, T., Cournapeau, D., Burovski, E., Peterson, P., Weckesser, W., Bright, J., van der Walt, S. J., Brett, M., Wilson, J., Millman, K. J., Mayorov, N., Nelson, A. R. J., Jones, E., Kern, R., Larson, E., ... van Mulbregt, P. (2020). SciPy 1.0: fundamental algorithms for scientific computing in Python. *Nature Methods*, 17(3), 261–272. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0686-2>
- Wang, Y., Huang, H., Rudin, C., & Shaposhnik, Y. (2021). Understanding How Dimension Reduction Tools Work: An Empirical Approach to Deciphering t-SNE, UMAP, TriMap, and PaCMAP for Data Visualization. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 22(201), 1–73. <http://jmlr.org/papers/v22/20-1061.html>
- Whitford, A. C., Blenkinsop, S., & Fowler, H. J. (2024). Atmospheric patterns associated with summer sub-daily rainfall extremes in western Europe. *Climate Dynamics*, 62(11), 10131–10152. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-024-07440-7>
- Zscheischler, J., Martius, O., Westra, S., Bevacqua, E., Raymond, C., Horton, R. M., van den Hurk, B., AghaKouchak, A., Jézéquel, A., Mahecha, M. D., Maraun, D., Ramos, A. M., Ridder, N. N., Thiery, W., & Vignotto, E. (2020). A typology of compound weather and climate events. *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, 1(7), 333–347. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-020-0060-z>

11. Annex A: Relationships between large-scale drivers and WPs

Figure 45: Plots showing time series of standardised DJF Atlantic Jet before (a) and after (b) de-trending, and box and whisker plots of standardised JF NAO corresponding to days assigned to each of the MO30 WPs (c). The lower, middle, and upper hinges of the boxplots show the 25th, 50th (median), and 75th percentiles of each distribution respectively, with the whiskers extending to the largest/smallest value no further than 1.5 times the IQR from the hinge and data beyond the end of the whiskers plotted individually.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 46: Plots showing time series of standardised DJF Aleutian Low before (a) and after (b) de-trending, and box and whisker plots of standardised JF NAO corresponding to days assigned to each of the MO30 WPs (c). The lower, middle, and upper hinges of the boxplots show the 25th, 50th (median), and 75th percentiles of each distribution respectively, with the whiskers extending to the largest/smallest value no further than 1.5 times the IQR from the hinge and data beyond the end of the whiskers plotted individually.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 47: Plots showing time series of standardised DJF Atlantic Dipole before (a) and after (b) de-trending, and box and whisker plots of standardised JF NAO corresponding to days assigned to each of the MO30 WPs (c). The lower, middle, and upper hinges of the boxplots show the 25th, 50th (median), and 75th percentiles of each distribution respectively, with the whiskers extending to the largest/smallest value no further than 1.5 times the IQR from the hinge and data beyond the end of the whiskers plotted individually.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 48: Plots showing time series of standardised ASO El Niño Southern Oscillation before (a) and after (b) de-trending, and box and whisker plots of standardised ASO El Niño Southern Oscillation corresponding to days assigned to each of the MO30 WPs (c). The lower, middle, and upper hinges of the boxplots show the 25th, 50th (median), and 75th percentiles of each distribution respectively, with the whiskers extending to the largest/smallest value no further than 1.5 times the IQR from the hinge and data beyond the end of the whiskers plotted individually.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 49: Plots showing time series of standardised OND Indian Ocean Dipole before (a) and after (b) de-trending, and box and whisker plots of standardised ASO OND Indian Ocean Dipole corresponding to days assigned to each of the MO30 WPs (c). The lower, middle, and upper hinges of the boxplots show the 25th, 50th (median), and 75th percentiles of each distribution respectively, with the whiskers extending to the largest/smallest value no further than 1.5 times the IQR from the hinge and data beyond the end of the whiskers plotted individually.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 50: Plots showing time series of standardised DJF Quasi-Biennial Oscillation before (a) and after (b) de-trending, and box and whisker plots of standardised DJF Quasi-Biennial Oscillation corresponding to days assigned to each of the MO30 WPs (c). The lower, middle, and upper hinges of the boxplots show the 25th, 50th (median), and 75th percentiles of each distribution respectively, with the whiskers extending to the largest/smallest value no further than 1.5 times the IQR from the hinge and data beyond the end of the whiskers plotted individually.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 51: Plots showing time series of standardised DJF Stratospheric Polar Vortex before (a) and after (b) de-trending, and box and whisker plots of standardised DJF Stratospheric Polar Vortex corresponding to days assigned to each of the MO30 WPs (c). The lower, middle, and upper hinges of the boxplots show the 25th, 50th (median), and 75th percentiles of each distribution respectively, with the whiskers extending to the largest/smallest value no further than 1.5 times the IQR from the hinge and data beyond the end of the whiskers plotted individually.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 52: Plots showing time series of standardised SON Urals Mean Sea Level Pressure before (a) and after (b) de-trending, and box and whisker plots of standardised SON Urals Mean Sea Level Pressure corresponding to days assigned to each of the MO30 WPs (c). The lower, middle, and upper hinges of the boxplots show the 25th, 50th (median), and 75th percentiles of each distribution respectively, with

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

the whiskers extending to the largest/smallest value no further than 1.5 times the IQR from the hinge and data beyond the end of the whiskers plotted individually.

Figure 53: Scatterplots showing the frequency of a given MO30 WP in January and February of each year, against the DJF Atlantic Jet of the same year, with each WP shown by a different plot facet.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 54: Scatterplots showing the frequency of a given MO30 WP in January and February of each year, against the DJF Aleutian Low of the same year, with each WP shown by a different plot facet.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 55: Scatterplots showing the frequency of a given MO30 WP in January and February of each year, against the DJF Atlantic Dipole of the same year, with each WP shown by a different plot facet.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 56: Scatterplots showing the frequency of a given MO30 WP in January and February of each year, against the OND Barents Kara Sea Ice Concentration of the same year, with each WP shown by a different plot facet.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 57: Scatterplots showing the frequency of a given MO30 WP in January and February of each year, against the ASO El Niño Southern Oscillation of the same year, with each WP shown by a different plot facet.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 58: Scatterplots showing the frequency of a given MO30 WP in January and February of each year, against the OND Indian Ocean Dipole of the same year, with each WP shown by a different plot facet.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 59: Scatterplots showing the frequency of a given MO30 WP in January and February of each year, against the DJF Quasi-Biennial Oscillation of the same year, with each WP shown by a different plot facet.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 60: Scatterplots showing the frequency of a given MO30 WP in January and February of each year, against the DJF Stratospheric Polar Vortex of the same year, with each WP shown by a different plot facet.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 61: Scatterplots showing the frequency of a given MO30 WP in January and February of each year, against the SON Urals MSLP in of the same year, with each WP shown by a different plot facet.

12. Annex B: Diagnostics of multiple linear regression models for Case Study

Figure 62: Multiple linear regression diagnostic plots for AtlJet causal effect on WP29.

Figure 63: Multiple linear regression diagnostic plots for NAO causal effect on WP 29.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 64: Multiple linear regression diagnostic plots for UralsMSLP causal effect on WP29.

Figure 65: Multiple linear regression diagnostic plots for AtlJet causal effect on WP30.

Deliverable 2.2 Report on understanding of weather types and large-scale climate drivers

Figure 66: Multiple linear regression diagnostic plots for NAO causal effect on WP30.